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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 7.5 – IMPACT ACTIVITIES (FINAL VERSION)

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Executive summary

The project THEIA^{XR} was launched in January 2023 as a new Research and Innovation Activity (RIA). The brand, the ecosystem as well as all dissemination activities had to be established anew. The Work Package (WP7), especially Task 7.1 therefore, focused on dissemination & ecosystem building. In this deliverable the work of WP7 and especially the subtasks in Task 7.1 and Task 7.2 are outlined, focusing mainly on the activities performed in the second phase of the project.

Task 7.1 covered the planning, carrying out and monitoring of communication and dissemination activities with the aim of building an ecosystem around the THEIA^{XR} objectives, development and results. The strategic goal was and still is to create a sustainable impact that will last beyond the end of the project by making the results of the research known to those who could benefit from them. During the second reporting period, the consortium members have been focusing on bringing information regarding the results with respect to the technical and societal results of the project and getting in closer contact with also potential end customers beyond the project consortium. In Month 36 of the project, a final recap shows that the planned activities could be delivered. Although the project has now been finalized, activities disseminating and exploiting results acquired in the project will continue.

Task 7.2 covers the exploitation of project key exploitable results (KER) and the development of an appropriate strategy to create the planned impact of THEIA^{XR}. In conjunction with Task 7.1 the stakeholder groups of the project have been identified and targeted during the dissemination events to support exploitation activities during the second half of the project. During the second phase “community outreach and initial results dissemination” (M13-M24) the assessment of the first available technological demonstrators has been performed to identify potential key exploitable results of the project.

In the second phase of the project, developments and decisions concerning the project dissemination, exploitation and innovation potential have been identified and the consortium has executed the defined communication strategies to leverage the ecosystem of the project. The exploitation activities have followed the framework introduced towards the planned impact KPIs. The final actions of Task 7.2 have been the collection of the exploitable technologies and the development of their market potential and business models respectively on how to achieve a sustainable impact beyond the duration of the THEIA^{XR} project.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable is intended to report on exploitation and impact creation methods and strategies that the THEIA^{XR} consortium has followed, as well as the relevant activities performed by the consortium until M36 of the project. This report is intended to be read by all consortium members.

1.1 Overview

Section 2 of this report provides a summary of the **communication activities** during the execution of the action. Additionally, the **dissemination activities** w.r.t., deliverables, publications, events and collaborations within the ecosystem of sister projects are described.

The **Section 3** lists and describes the **exploitable results** of Task 7.2 in more detail. Additionally, each result is briefly described from an innovation point of view. During the reporting period a brief business analysis was performed for each topic to frame the result in the context of external and internal opportunities and market potentials and further investment needed to launch a potential product or service. The project consortium has identified in **18 exploitable results** from the development activities. The composition according to the exploitation type is depicted in Table 1. Notably due to the type of action, the project THEIA^{XR} is considered as research and innovation action, approximately a quarter of the innovation items are applicable in future R&D projects or within an educational setting, mainly since the final TRL level achievable during the project duration remains low. The amount of exploitation activities (9) foreseen to commercialization across the project consortium showcases the strong commitment of all partners towards innovative market solutions. The strong interest from academia in contract research (4) is a positive surprise since it supports the European Market to match a rapidly transforming technological and socio-economic reality towards a digital future.

Table 1: Distribution of Results based on Exploitation Type

Type of Exploitation	Nr. of Result/Innovation Item
Education	1
Application in new R&D Project	4
Commercialization	8
Application in Contract Research	4

Section 4 (Risk Assessment of exploitable Results) provides a risk assessment for each individual exploitable result across six different pre-defined thread categories. Additionally, it summarizes the findings on a project level by combining the individual findings.

The focus of **Section 5** within the report is to conclude the **third pillar of the exploitation framework** namely the business strategy of individual project results following the methods described in the first version of this deliverable. These considerations have been performed on two different levels. Firstly, on project partner level, where a differentiation between industrial and academic partners have been made, and secondly on project result levels. Here the individual result owners have assessed the exploitation potential given the findings of the experimentation and validation in WP6.

The domain specific aspects have been summarized in individual **use-case specific business canvas** in **Section 6** since an isolated examination on a technology level is rather limited. Most of the technologies developed and demonstrated in THEIA^{XR} can be integrated cross-domain and only together with other results the customer/end-user needs are fulfilled.

2 Dissemination and Communication Impact

2.1 Communication

2.1.1 Communication Channels

THEIA^{XR} Website

The THEIA^{XR} website is hosted and authored by TTC as coordinator of the project. It provides a comprehensive description of the THEIA^{XR} project, presents the consortium, the use cases as well as the most current news and results. Reading through the website, the interested audience is provided with all relevant material to get a status of the current activities performed in the project.

This website is also a prominent example of the strong project identity, created at the beginning of the project. The logo is designed to present all three use cases including, with the colours ranging from darker to lighter ones representing the “making the invisible visible” through XR.

Figure 1: THEIA^{XR} Website – Landing Page

LinkedIn Presence

LinkedIn has been used as our main social media channel for the project. A corresponding site has been created at the beginning of the project and since then, continuously and strategically has been maintained

and enlarged. Up until writing of this deliverable, the THEIA^{XR} project has attracted 500 followers and the connected LinkedIn newsletter, published on a semi-annual basis, has 213 subscribers.

In the period from project start until writing this deliverable, THEIA^{XR} has reached 70.007 impressions on the posts and attracted 933 visitors to the LinkedIn site. Besides these pure numbers, interested exchange and promising connections for the project were established via LinkedIn (representatives from Komatsu, Liebherr, Claas, Rosenbauer, Sandvik, ...).

Figure 2: THEIA^{XR} LinkedIn Site

YouTube Presence

As mentioned before in the deliverable, the presence on YouTube does not have the reason to establish a further social network that is strategically maintained. However, it is more a platform for videos to be linked to the THEIA^{XR} website and to be spread on LinkedIn. During the second phase of the project, the YouTube channel has been used to upload and link videos showing results of the project.

YOUTUBE PICTURE

Newsletter

As introduced before, the THEIA^{XR} project has established a semi-annual newsletter that is populated over LinkedIn, but as well provided as PDF, published on Zenodo and linked on the THEIA^{XR} website. Up until writing of this deliverable 5 editions of the newsletter have been published.

Figure 3: THEIA^{XR} LinkedIn Newsletter

Newsletter edition	Zenodo views	Zenodo download	LinkedIn impressions ¹
THEIA^{XR} newsletter edition No 1	67	59	0
THEIA^{XR} newsletter edition No 2	78	110	0
THEIA^{XR} newsletter edition No 3	32	49	12

¹ Only impressions from 2025 are taken into account.

THEIA^{XR} newsletter edition No 4	23	36	93
THEIA^{XR} newsletter edition No 5	29	15	458
THEIA ^{XR} newsletter edition No. 6 ²	-	-	-

Table 2: THEIA^{XR} Newsletter Analytics

Zenodo

THEIA^{XR} has created a Zenodo community to provide the results generated in the project to a broader audience. As already introduced in the previous chapters, the content provided there is linked to the THEIA^{XR} website and shared on LinkedIn.

By the time of writing, there are 54 uploads on the THEIA^{XR} Zenodo community, containing public deliverables, publications, presentations, theses, videos and marketing material. The top download is a scientific paper published by partner TUG, which has been downloaded 260 times.

Figure 4: THEIA^{XR} Zenodo Community³

2.1.2 Communication Material

In the first period, the THEIA^{XR} project had already created a number of communication material, that has been extensively used during the project. This included among others the THEIA^{XR} project flyer, co-design flyer and multiple roll-ups, which were mentioned in the first version of this deliverable.

In the second phase of the project, additional dedicated communication material has been created to inform the external about specific activities to take place within the project or to highlight the results of the project. These are shared online as well as on as many events possible.

Result One-Pagers

To explicitly highlight the main results of the project, individual one-pagers were created that describe the results of the separate partners. These one-pagers give a high-level description of a single results of the project, including the partner that was responsible for them. These one-pagers are available on the website where they can be downloaded.

² At the moment of writing the deliverable, the final newsletter is in production

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/theia-xr>

Figure 5: Selection of THEIA^{XR} Result One-Pagers

Privacy Guidelines Flyers

Within the project, guidelines for privacy and ethics in XR implementation for Off-Highway Mobile Machinery has been developed by partner UL. To bring this information in an easy way to a large audience, an intuitive flyer with sufficient information has been developed that highlights the most important information regarding the guidelines, including a description and a place where these guidelines can be downloaded. In Figure 6, the flyer of the guidelines is depicted, which has been distributed at various events where THEIA^{XR} was present.

Figure 6: Privacy Guidelines Flyer

Event Flyers

On the 12th December 2025, a webinar was organized by THEIA^{XR} with the title “Privacy and Ethics in XR and AI”. Presenters from our project and from AI Factory Austria, CODE4EV, sister project DIDYMOS-XR and AI5Innovation gave an impulse talk on various topics.

In the weeks before the webinar, we inform the audience about the webinar and additionally, we created flyers to be distributed at various events.

Figure 7: Flyer announcing Privacy and Ethics Workshop organized by THEIA^{XR}

2.2 THEIA^{XR} Dissemination

2.2.1 Public Deliverables

THEIA^{XR} produces a large number of public deliverables (see Figure XX), that, once approved, will be provided through Zenodo and spread via the already established communication channels.

Out of a total of 33 public deliverables, 12 have already been accepted and published on Zenodo (dark blue background in Table 3). Of the submitted deliverables that were public, 4 of them needed some updates. As they will be accepted in the final review, these are not released for publication yet (light blue background in Table 3). The other public deliverables will be made available as soon as they are accepted by the technical reviewers.

Public Deliverables	Zenodo views	Zenodo download
Use Case Specifications (first version)	43	38
Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version)	54	50
HMI content list (first version)	35	41
Context-of-use Analysis (first version)	-	-
Interaction modality assignment	25	36
Interaction sequence models (first version)	22	70
Privacy requirements	25	31
Interaction concepts (first version)	27	26
Concept of virtual user interface (first version)	35	94
Evaluation Report (first version)	-	-
Integrated THEIA ^{XR} technologies and methodologies and use case implementation (first version)	31	37

Interaction Scenarios (first version)	-	-
Deployment, testing and demonstration of the THEIA ^{XR} use cases (first version)	-	-
Prototypes for privacy-related questions (first version)	27	30
Impact activities (first version)	28	35
Design guidelines and validation reports for privacy (first version)	45	36
Use Case Specification (final version)	-	-
Context-of-use Analysis (final version)	-	-
Validation and evaluation (first version)	-	-
HMI content list (final version)	-	-
Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (final version)	-	-
Interaction sequence models (final version)	-	-
Interaction Scenarios (final version)	-	-
Prototypes for privacy-related questions (final version)	-	-
Interaction concepts (final version)	-	-
Concept of virtual user interface (final version)	-	-
Integrated THEIA ^{XR} technologies and methodologies and use case implementation (final version)	-	-
Deployment, testing and demonstration of the THEIA ^{XR} use cases (final version)	-	-
Evaluation Report (final version)	-	-
Validation and evaluation (final version)	-	-
Privacy assessment results	-	-
XR Design guidelines	-	-
Impact activities	-	-
Design guidelines and validation reports for privacy (final version)	-	-

Table 3: THEIA^{XR} public deliverables

2.2.2 Publications

The THEIA^{XR} track records of scientific publications shows a valuable number of publications in journals and conference proceedings. At the moment of writing this deliverable, 36 publications have been created, which includes 9 Bachelor Theses and 6 Master Theses.

Some of the major conferences and/or events in the THEIA^{XR} domain have been targeted and publications were accepted. Some examples of the major conferences have been the following:

- CHI 2025: CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems
- International Journal of Human-Computer Studies
- EuroXR 2024 and 2025
- International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications (VISAPP)
- IEEE VR Conference
- International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy
- IEEE Transactions of Visualization and Computer Graphics
- International Conference on Computer Graphics, Visualization and Computer Vision (WSCG)
- Computers & Graphics Journal

All of the publications are available on the [THEIA^{XR} website](#), and the majority of them have references to repositories where the publications can be freely read and downloaded (e.g., Zenodo, institute repositories, etc). This was one of the promises of THEIA^{XR} to make as many results as possible open to the public.

2.2.3 Events

The following chapter will give insights on the project public appearances at the various conferences, expos, industrial fairs and presentations that were attended and held since July 2024.

Stereopsia 2024

This year, THEIA^{XR} had a booth at the Stereopsia, presenting the various technologies developed within the project. The main demonstrator was the virtual world and remote operation demonstrator of the reach stacker, which was presented by Kaj Helin and Andrea Alesani from partner VTT. Furthermore, Anastasia Sergeeva from partner UL presented the first version of the guidelines and interacted with many other visitors and participants about the usability and applicability of the defined guidelines.

Figure 8: THEIA^{XR} at Stereopsia 2024

AWE Europe 2024

Partner CREA attended the AWE Europe in Vienna, Austria from 29th to 30th October. They presented their simulation environment to a larger industrial and scientific community, highlighting how the virtualization of off-highway machines can benefit the usage of XR, making the invisible visible.

Figure 9: Crenex at AWE EU 2024

Agritechnica 2025

During the Agritechnica 2025 in Hannover, which is the world's leading trade fair for agricultural technology, THEIA^{XR} was represented at the stand of TTControl. Martijn Rooker and Gerald Fritz-Mayer were present and discussed with external partners and companies the results and importance of the project to the Off-Highway domain, especially targeting agricultural machines, like tractors, harvesters, etc.

Figure 10: TTControl @ Agritechnica 2025

AR/VR Coalition Meeting

On the 11th and the 12th of February 2025, the THEIA^{XR} project was invited to a special session of the AR/VR Coalition, which was held in Brussels, Belgium. During this session, multiple EU projects were present, including the sister project SharedSpace and SUN-XR. The projects were given the opportunity to present their work towards the member of the AR/VR coalition and the members of European Commission. Martijn Rooker presented the project and participated in further discussions on how the results of the project can aid the upcoming Virtual Worlds PPP.

Figure 11: Martijn Rooker, presenting the project at the AR/VR Coalition Meeting in Brussels

bauma 2025

The bauma, which is the international trade fair for construction machinery, building material machines, mining machines, construction vehicles and construction equipment, is the world's largest trade fair in the construction industry. This trade fair offered excellent opportunities for the THEIA^{XR} project to present their results to a target audience that is perfectly aligned with the scope of the project.

Partner TUD presented their Use Case 3 demonstrator at the booth of the Technical University Dresden (see Figure 12). They had visitors from research and industry, showing high interest in their extended reality solution. Partner TTC also had a booth at the trade fair, where discussions were held and results were presented that highlighted how construction machines can benefit from XR technologies and make control of such machines can be safer for a human operator.

Figure 12: TUD with UC3 demonstrator at the bauma 2025

Additionally, partner TUD was nominated with their results for the bauma Innovation Award 2025 in the category [Research](#). A [video](#) was submitted that presented the individual results for the construction domain. At the end, TUD results managed to receive the second place

Finalisten 2025 | Kategorie: Forschung

- Center Construction Robotics (RWTH Aachen)
- Friedrich Alexander Universität Erlangen Nürnberg
- RWTH Aachen University
- Technische Hochschule Köln - F06
- Technische Hochschule Ostwestfalen-Lippe
- Technische Universität Dresden
- Technische Universität München fmi

Nominiert für:

bauma

Innovationspreis

2025

Ideas moving us forward

Figure 13: Partner TUD nominated as one of the finalists for the bauma Innovation Award 2025 in the category Research

InterAlpin 2025

One of the highlights of the project, was the participation at the InterAlpin tradefair, which is the international trade fair for cable car engineering and alpine technologies, which took place from 5th till 7th May in Innsbruck, Austria. It is the lead trade fair for partner PRIN and they provided the THEIA^{XR} project the

opportunity to demonstrate the results of the use case 1 demonstrator (see Figure 14). This event provided two opportunities to the consortium. On the one hand to present the results to a large industrial and scientific community, all dedicated to the alpine domain and secondly, to interact with a large selection of operators of snow groomers. The demonstrator attracted large crowds, wanting to explore the virtual experience of driving a snow groomer. Additionally, the majority of operators were also requested to fill out a collection of questionnaires, giving the consortium valuable insights in the usability and acceptability of the developed technologies. Partners PRIN, HdM, CREA, UL and TTC attended the trade fair and spent three intense days interacting with people.

Figure 14: THEIA^{XR} at the InterAlpin 2025, demonstrating UC1 and interacting with operators

World Usability Day Stuttgart 2025

Tanja Brodbeck and Sarah Bacher from HdM presented parts of their work on Co-Design in XR usage in the Off-Highway domain at the World Usability Day Stuttgart 2025. The [presentation](#) highlighted how the developed Co-Design methodology was used within the project and how this approach and the direct interaction with end-users of technologies can influence the design and development.

Figure 15: Tanja Brodbeck and Sarah Bacher, HdM presenting their work in the THEIA^{XR} project at WUD 2025

EuroXR 2024

The THEIA^{XR} consortium was largely represented at the EuroXR 2024, which was held in Athens, Greece from November 27th to November 29th 2024. Martijn Rooker presented the THEIA^{XR} project in the EU project pitches session. Additionally, together with the sister projects DIDYMOS-XR, SharedSpace, SUN-XR, Cortex2 and Luminous, a special session was organised where each project presented two topics from their respective research. The session was moderated by Martijn Rooker. Thomas Kernbauer (TUG) and Manuel Kulzer-Braun (HdM) presented work in this session. Furthermore, Tanja Brodbeck and Manuel Kulzer-Braun had a presentation on involving the human operator in the design process. Jerome Perrot (Haption) also presented a poster on haptic feedback and Andrea Alesani and Kaj Helin from VTT showed the reach stacker demonstration to the larger audience.

Figure 16: THEIA^{XR} represented at the EuroXR 2024, Athens,Greece

EuroXR 2025

During the EuroXR 2025, which was held from 3rd till 5th of September in Winterthur, Switzerland, THEIA^{XR} organized a workshop on the topic of “Preserving Ethics and Privacy in the Dawn of Industrial Extended Reality”. Anastasia Sergeeva from partner UL hosted this workshop. Additionally, she participated in the European Project Panel Session on the “Future of XR”. It was once again a great possibility to interact with other researchers and see where the future of XR is taking us.

Figure 17: Partner UL at EuroXR 2025

Metaverse Standards Forum Webinar

Anastasia Sergeeva from partner UL was invited to speak at the Ethics Summit from the Metaverse Standards Forum on the 18th July 2025. She joined a panel with people from among other, Meta, Siemens, Samsung, Stanford University, Cornell Tech, Johns Hopkins University, etc.

They discussed some of the most important topics on the ethics in the Metaverse, where UL presented the THEIA^{XR} approach with respect to Ethics and how it was included in the project.

iVT Expo 2024

During the iVT Expo 2024 in Köln, THEIA^{XR} was represented at the stand of TTControl, enabling external partner and companies to interact with the colleagues of TTControl and discuss the results and importance of the project to the Off-Highway domain.

Figure 18: THEIA^{XR} at the iVT 2024

iVT Expo 2025, Off-Highway Evolution Summit

THEIA^{XR} was represented at the stand of the project coordinator TTControl and project coordinator Martijn Rooker was invited to the Off-Highway Evolution Summit in the session “Human-Machine Interface (HMI)” to present the project. This session focused on topics like Enhancing user interaction with intuitive dashboards, AR/VR integration and voice-controlled systems, which covered many of the topics of the project.

Figure 19: Martijn Rooker presenting at the iVT expo 2025 summit

The session was a lively discussion, between the presenters and the audience addressing many interesting topics covering the future off-highway machines.

Horizon Europe Day (Luxinnovation)

The University of Luxembourg organized a Horizon Europe Day at their location on the 5th December 2024. It provided opportunities to understand the Horizon Europe funding process, receive guidance on how to navigate eligibility criteria, initiate collaborations with new partners and learn from currently running projects. Anastasia Sergeeva presented the THEIA^{XR} project as an example of a successful project and provided information on concepts of the project.

Figure 20: Partner UL at Horizon Europe Day

UnitedXR 2025

The UnitedXR 2025 was targeted as the final dissemination event of the THEIA^{XR} project, where we also hosted our final consortium meeting. During this event, which was from 8th December to 10th December in Brussels, Belgium, we presented our three use cases with their respective demonstrators.

The UnitedXR is the combination of Stereopsia and AWE, forming a large network driving XR growth in Europe and reshape the global immersive landscape. This offered an excellent opportunity for the THEIA^{XR} consortium to present the final results of the project to a larger public, scientific and industrial audience.

The consortium of THEIA^{XR} have been involved in many activities on the UnitedXR 2025, including the following:

- [Press release](#)
- EU Project Pitch session
- [Media Walkthrough](#)
- Panel discussion on ethics (Partner UL)
- Presentation in scientific track (Partners UL and HdM)
- Guided Tour: Education Training
- Final project consortium meeting
- Three days booth presence showing the demonstrators

Figure 21: THEIA^{XR} consortium present at the UnitedXR

Exchanging information with other European projects and industrial players showed that the results of the projects are a valid asset to the immersive domain and form an excellent basis for future research and work.

Webinar on “Privacy and Ethics in XR and AI”

As mentioned before, on the 12th of December 2025, THEIA^{XR} organized a webinar on the topic of “Privacy and Ethics in XR and AI”. For this webinar, we invited an excellent group of experts in the field of XR and AI to share their views and expertise in form of impulse talks to a large industrial and scientific audience. The following optics were discussed:

- “Preserving Ethics and Privacy in the Dawn of Industrial XR” by Anastasia Sergeeva, University of Luxembourg (THEIA-XR)
- “Trustworthy AI” by Dr. Peter Biegelbauer, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AI Factory Austria AI:AT)
- “The Role of Standards Today and Tomorrow” by Ilija Ilić, Austrian Standards (CODE4EV)
- “Ethical Issues in XR applications based digital twins” by Irma Pöder, Trilateral Research (DIDYMOS-XR)
- “Human Oversight in view of super-human AI” by Bernhard Nessler, SCCH Software Competence Center Hagenberg (EDIH AI5innovation)

During the webinar, a lively discussion and many interesting discussions appeared resulting in many topics open for future research and possible collaboration between the presenters and the audience. Figure 22 provide some impressions from the webinar.

Figure 22: Impressions of the Webinar on “Privacy and Ethics in XR and AI”

The following statistics can be derived from the webinar with respect to the presenters and audience that have registered to the session (see Figure 23). In total, we received 52 registrations.

Type of Organization	Percentage
Academia & Research	50,94%
Academia & Research,Civil Society & NGOs	3,77%
Academia & Research,Government & Public Sector	3,77%
Civil Society & NGOs	9,43%
Government & Public Sector	1,89%
Industry & Business	28,30%
Industry & Business,Civil Society & NGOs	1,89%
Total	100,00%

Figure 23: Statistics of participants to the webinar

2.2.4 Sister Projects Cooperation

During the second phase of the project, we continued the cooperation with our sister projects DIDYMOS-XR, SUN-XR and ShareSpace. Additionally, close interaction has also been with the Cortex2 project and with the XR4HUMAN project, which is a CSA co-creating living guidance documents on ethics. Various events have taken place, where we interacted with these projects.

EuroXR 2024

At the EuroXR 2024, held in Athens, Greece, a special session was organized with all sister projects and other projects (SUN-XR, DIDYMOS-XR, ShareSpace, Cortex2 and Luminous). There were two sessions organized. One where each project was able to pitch their project and the second one, where each project as invited to provide two technical presentations highlighting some of the impressive results that have been achieved so far.

Figure 24: Representatives of the sister projects at EuroXR 2024

Additionally, a panel session was organized with representatives of the sister projects, discussing the future of eXtended Reality.

Figure 25: Panel discussion on the future of XR.

Event “Do Tech Ethics (Actually) Work?”

In July 2025, Anastasia Sergeeva from partner UL was invited to London to participate in a workshop titled “Do Tech Ethics (Actually) Work” organized by our sister project ShareSpace. For THEIA^{XR}, it was an excellent opportunity to show the ethics-in-practice challenges we are facing (and overcoming) in our project, and to connect with more people who understand the role of ethics in all the changes new technologies (AI and XR as two rather bright examples) bring to work and society.

Figure 26: Anastasia Sergeeva presenting the ethics topics from THEIA^{XR} at the workshop in London

Workshop “Beyond Just Privacy: Addressing Ethical Questions in XR Spaces (EU Projects Experiences)”

On the 15th of April, partner UL hosted a workshop titled “Beyond Just Privacy: Addressing Ethical Questions in XR Spaces (EU Projects Experiences)” as part of the work towards developing Ethics and Privacy guidelines for XR in Off-Highway machinery.

The goal of the project was to bring in the expertise of our sister projects DIDYMOS-XR, SUN-XR and ShareSpace. In all these projects, ethics and privacy are treated with great importance, not just as background concerns, but as key factors that form the entire process of technological development. We were also fortunate to have on board the XR4HUMAN project that places ethics at the core of its effort through the development of a Code of Conduct of Immersive Technologies.

Figure 27: Partners from sister projects present at UL for the Ethics Workshop

3 Exploitable Results

The following section provides the final status of identified exploitable results generated by THEIA^{XR}. The goal is to achieve the widest possible development and validation of technologies and methodologies in order to enable the possibility for a pre-commercial exploitation upon successful demonstration. The individual exploitation plans are not intended to be exhaustive: instead, there is a stronger focus on the particular exploitation paths which are a-priori more relevant for THEIA^{XR} foreseeable KERs.

3.1 List of Exploitable Results

The following table (Table 4) resumes a preliminary analysis of the potential exploitable outputs from the project. It summarizes the innovation item, the leader of the result and characterizes the type of exploitation as planned by the partner. Furthermore, the major business sector was identified to illustrate the primary market, which will be targeted during market launch.

Table 4: List of Exploitable Results

ID	Result/Innovation	Leader	Type of Exploitation	Sector(s) of application	Possible Exploitable product or measure
ID-01	High performance computing platform for the execution of algorithms/applications	TTC	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Mobile machines, construction machines	High performance computing platform for the execution of algorithms/applications to perform process optimization, advanced driver assistance functions (e.g. person & object detection, avoid/reduce errors etc.) autonomous operations in off-highway applications.
ID-02	Multimodal Cabin Mock-Up	TUD	Contract research: (new contracts signed by the research group with external clients)	Mobile machines, construction machines	Test and Development environment for fast prototyping of cabin technologies, HMIs and assistance systems for mobile machinery, e.g. construction machines.
ID-03	Laser and DLP Projection System for Outdoor Projective Augmented Reality	TUG	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Automotive, Heavy Machinery Sector	Hardware Blueprint and rugged Prototype for further research and development
ID-04	Panoramic 360° Thermal Camera	TUG	Commercialisation: deployment of a	Human-machine	Hardware Blueprint and rugged Prototype

	with 360° RGB Images		novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	interfaces (HMI), Automotive, Heavy Machinery Sector	for further research and development
ID-05	Remote Driving Experience with prototypical remote-controlled vehicle and VR integration	TUG	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Automotive, Heavy Machinery Sector	Hardware Blueprint and rugged Prototype for further research and development
ID-06	Algorithms and Methods for Infrastructure Visualization outdoors by way of AR	TUG	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Automotive, Heavy Machinery Sector	Software Blueprint and prototypes for further research and development
ID-07	Design Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Off-Highway Machinery Domain	UL	Contract research: (new contracts signed by the research group with external clients)	Off-Highway Machinery (including, but not limited to the use cases of the project), broader educational sector (courses/module in industrial xr design education)	Contract-based work and consulting for the ethical design of XR implementations for Off-Highway Machinery domain, educational modulus for educational projects in ethical XR
ID-08	Transdisciplinary co-design approach for technical research and innovation projects	HdM	Implementation of a new university - course (Note that a training course is a service)	Education, software and/or hardware development	University lectures, enterprise consulting services
ID-09	Validated, end-user-approved XR/digital interface function, information and interaction concepts for off-highway vehicle cabins	HdM	Contract research: (new contracts signed by the research group with external clients)	Construction, logistics, agriculture, mining, forestry	Enterprise consulting services, collaboration and contract-based work in externally funded projects
ID-10	AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept	VTT	Contract research: (new contracts signed by the research group with external clients)	Off-Highway Machinery Segment	Consulting service, proof-of-concept, UI and concept design

ID_11	Snow groomer operator training simulator	CREA	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Snow groomer market	A simulator for training snow groomer operators. The final product can have two different models. The light version can be a kind of suit case version having laptop computer and the controls are mounted on the edge of an office table. The high end version could have a seat mounted on a motion platform.
ID_12	Haptic track controls unit	HAP	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Off-highway machinery - Snow grooming	Track controls unit (Product, Hardware)
ID_13	Vibrotactile handle concept for force-feedback devices	HAP	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Haptic Devices	Vibrotactile handle (Product, hardware), driving software (Product, software)
ID_14	6-axis haptic arm for use in demanding environments	HAP	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Haptic Devices	6DoF force feedback device for demanding environments
ID_15	Software bridge for interfacing 3rd party simulators and game engines with Haption force-feedback devices	HAP	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Haptic Devices	Software bridge (Product, software)
ID_16	Force and tactile assistance function concepts for off-highway vehicles	HAP	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Off-highway vehicle OEMs	Firmware / Software implementing haptic assistance functions
ID_17	AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept	KAL	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Off-Highway cargo handling Machinery Segment	Novel AR-Enhanced Operator Terminal/UI
ID_18	Snow groomer simulator	PRIN	Commercialisation: deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)	Snow groomer market	A snow grooming simulator exists of a operator cabin with original controls and a simulation software which allows to move

					and control a snow groomer in a virtual world.
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In addition to the identified exploitable results the project consortium and result owners (leads) investigated the constraints prior to commercial or non-commercial use, time-to-market estimation, and major further development required prior to a go-to-market activity. These are depicted in the following section.

3.2 Constraints/ Time-to-Market / IP Protection / TRL Assessment

Table 5 resumes the analysis given in Section 3.1 and extends the potential exploitable outputs.

Table 5: Properties of preliminary Innovation Items

ID	Result/Innovation	Constraints prior to Usage	Timetable of Usage after End of the Project	Prerequisite for go-to-market	TRL Baseline (M0) -> Target (M36)
ID-01	High performance computing platform for the execution of algorithms/applications	Market penetration, Limitations in computational resources	3-5 years	Improve HW and SW toolchain for customers	3-5
ID-02	Multimodal Cabin Mock-Up	Resources	1-3 years	product ready version, certification	3-5
ID-03	Laser and DLP Projection System for Outdoor Projective Augmented Reality	Commercialization Costs	2-5 years	Product development stage, Commercialization & Certification	2-5
ID-04	Panoramic 360° Thermal Camera with 360° RGB Images	Commercialization Costs	2-5 years	Product development stage, Commercialization & Certification	3-5
ID-05	Remote Driving Experience with prototypical remote-controlled vehicle and VR integration	Commercialization Costs	2-5 years	Product development stage, Commercialization & Certification	2-4
ID-06	Algorithms and Methods for Infrastructure Visualization outdoors by way of AR	Commercialization Costs	2-5 years	Product development stage, Commercialization & Certification	2-4
ID-07	Design Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Off-Highway Machinery Domain	not applicable	immediately	not applicable	n.a.

ID-08	Transdisciplinary co-design approach for technical research and innovation projects	Market awareness	immediately	Further scientific validation and documentation	2-4
ID-09	Validated, end-user-approved XR/digital interface function, information and interaction concepts for off-highway vehicle cabins	Resources for Consulting Services	immediately	Further scientific validation and documentation	3-5
ID-10	AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept	Market acceptance, legal concerns regarding GDPR (people tracking)	2-3 years	Customization of UI & concept adaptation	3-5
ID_11	Snow groomer operator training simulator	Market penetration	one year	Improve hardware setup, commercialization of software modules	3-6
ID_12	Haptic track controls unit	Commercialization Costs	2-3 years	Improvement of HW, Commercialization & Certification	3-5
ID_13	Vibrotactile handle concept for force-feedback devices	Commercialization Costs	1-2 years	Improvement of HW & SW, Commercialization & Certification	3-6
ID_14	6-axis haptic arm for use in demanding environments	Commercialization Costs	2-3 years	Improvement of HW, Commercialization & Certification	3-5
ID_15	Software bridge for interfacing 3rd party simulators and game engines with Haption force-feedback devices	Commercialization Costs	1-2 years	Improvement of SW, Commercialization & Certification	3-6
ID_16	Force and tactile assistance function concepts for off-highway vehicles	Commercialization Costs	2-3 years	Improvement of SW, Commercialization & Certification	3-5
ID_17	AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept	Commercialization Costs	2-3 years	Improvement of HW & SW, Commercialization & Certification	3-5
ID_18	Snow groomer simulator	Limitation in simulation accuracy and complexity	3 years	Improvement of simulation behaviour and complex model and accessory configuration.	4-6

The following section provides the detailed analysis of each individual project result (KER) concerning **(i) value proposition, (ii) impact creation** and **(iii) exploitation potential**.

3.3 Detailed Exploitable Results

The following section provides the detailed analysis of all key exploitable results (KER) identified by each individual partner in the project. The categories and attributes map the essential aspects needed to plan the exploitation and business model for the individual KER. The process begins by identifying the KER and providing a brief title, followed by a detailed description that clarifies what the result is and how it addresses specific needs or challenges. Furthermore, the description lists what product or service will be developed from this result, the market sector it targets, and the intended customers or users.

The analysis also provides considerations of legal, normative, or ethical requirements that must be met for market entry, as well as an estimate of the investment needed and the expected timeline to bring the result to market. The structured summary provides details on the problems the KER addresses, compares it to current solutions, and highlight what makes the approach unique or superior.

Additionally, the result owner provided an estimation of the potential market size, the maturity and acceptance of the market, and the competitive landscape (where possible), including main competitors and potential early adopters. Finally, the result owners anticipated the market uptake, ensuring that all key business and exploitation aspects are considered for commercialization activities beyond the project scope. Overall, these categories structured a potential exploitation strategy and an individual business model for each KER, ensuring all key aspects—from technical description to market and financial planning—are considered for successfully commercializing the results out of THEIA^{XR}.

3.3.1 Result ID-01: High performance computing platform for the execution of algorithms/applications

KER 01 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-01
Short Title of the KER	High performance computing platform for the execution of algorithms/applications
In depth description of the Result	Off-Highway mobile machines are often deployed in harsh environments with limited connectivity possibilities, thus not capable of transferring collected sensor data to a cloud computing solution for processing. Therefore, it is important that a mobile machine is equipped with embedded computing capabilities, handling the majority of the data directly on the machine. Additionally, to be applicable in mobile machines, the embedded platform must also be able to interface with various sensors and actuators. Within the project, an embedded platform with software architecture has been developed that enables to collect data from multiple sensors via industrially accepted interfaces and is able to provide data directly to the human operator via the connected output devices.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	ECU Controller (Product, Hardware) and Software Environment for Integration and Development
Market Sector addressed	Off-Highway Machinery Segment
Target Customer/User addressed	Off-Highway OEMs, System integrators

Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	SIL 2 (EN 61508) / PL d (EN ISO 13849) / AgPL d (ISO 25119) / ASIL C (ISO 26262)
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	additional investment of approx. €500k -€ 1 Mio
Time to Market	two up to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Cutting edge Hailo-8 AI Accelerator, capable of handling data directly on the machine. Limiting costs for transferring data to external computing resources (e.g., Cloud computing). Currently, few market-ready solutions with AI capabilities are entering the off-highway market.
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	Ruggedized embedded computing platform, capable of connecting four displays and multiple sensors.
Product/Service Market Size	There is currently no market for high-performance computing platform in this domain. We expect to become one of the first movers.
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Emerging: there is growing demand, and few offerings are available
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	market leader with turn-key solutions (e.g. John Deere), Tier1 Suppliers (e.g. Bosch Rexroth)
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Off-Highway OEMS (e.g., Prinoth, Rosenbauer, Palfinger, ...)
External Experts/Partners to be involved	None
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	10M€+
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	15M€+
Expected Market Take-up	100M€+

3.3.2 Result ID-02: Multimodal Cabin Mock-Up

KER 02 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-02
Short Title of the KER	Multimodal Cabin Mock-Up

In depth description of the Result	<p>The Multimodal Cabin Mock-Up (MCMU) is a research platform designed to emulate the operator environment of mobile machinery, such as excavators, tractors, forestry harvesters, mining vehicles, or construction loaders. It provides a flexible, reconfigurable, and instrumented cabin environment for studying human-machine interaction (HMI), ergonomic design, sensor integration, and operator assistance technologies under controlled experimental conditions.</p> <p>This mock-up does not function as a real machine but serves as a simulator-grade testbed that reproduces the sensory, spatial, and control aspects of mobile machinery operation. It allows researchers to test multimodal interfaces—including visual, auditory, tactile, and haptic feedback systems—to assess how different interface designs influence performance, safety, comfort, and cognitive load.</p>
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Test and Development environment for fast prototyping of cabin technologies, HMIs and assistance systems for mobile machinery, e.g. construction machines.
Market Sector addressed	Off-Highway Machinery Segment
Target Customer/User addressed	Off-Highway OEMs, off-highway cabin and interior supplier
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	
Cost to bring product/service to the “market” (before actual Exploitation)	500k EURO
Time to Market	1-3 years
Problems addressed and current solutions	
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	Compared to development simulation environments, the multimodal cabin mock-up offers a holistic solution for cabin simulations including physical and visual HMI-components that can be customized for prototyping purposes
Product/Service Market Size	
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Non-existent: customers are not yet buying such products
Competition	Patchy, no major players
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	e.g. MEVEA
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Fritzmeyer, Grammar

External Experts/Partners to be involved	None
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	1 M EURO
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	0,5 M EURO
Expected Market Take-up	10 M EURO

3.3.3 Result ID-03: Laser and DLP Projection System for Outdoor Projective Augmented Reality

KER 03 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-03
Short Title of the KER	Laser and DLP Projection System for Outdoor Projective Augmented Reality
In depth description of the Result	A hardware prototype incorporating a laser, a DLP projector, a camera and a compute unit in a common housing to perform projective outdoor Augmented Reality based on environment information and control input
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Hardware Blueprint and rugged Prototype for further research and development
Market Sector addressed	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Automotive, Heavy Machinery Sector
Target Customer/User addressed	HMI OEMs, System integrators
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	potentially ISO9001
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. ~300k€
Time to Market	Two to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Head-worn or handheld AR devices are hardly usable in in-vehicle or in-machine operations. Projective AR can visualize information relative to a machine or vehicle, without the need for additional gadgets.
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	The system is unique und rugged, such that it can be deployed in one or the other way in outdoor environments.
Product/Service Market Size	~100M€

Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Non-existent: customers are not yet buying such products
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Non-existent concerning this proposition
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Partnership with early adopters with particular requirements, several interested companies
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Licensing and funding of further collaborative research projects, 200k/yr
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~200k€ annually
Expected Market Take-up	10%

3.3.4 Result ID-04: Panoramic 360° Thermal Camera with 360° RGB Images

KER 04 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-04
Short Title of the KER	Panoramic 360° Thermal Camera with 360° RGB Images
In depth description of the Result	A prototype consisting of 6 thermal and 2 RGB cameras, enabling the observation of full 360° field of view in both the thermal and the visible domain.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Hardware Blueprint and rugged Prototype for further research and development
Market Sector addressed	Sensor Developers, System Integrators, Camera Manufacturers
Target Customer/User addressed	HMI OEMs, System integrators
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	ISO9001
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. ~1M€
Time to Market	Two to three years

Problems addressed and current solutions	Thermography is beyond the human visual spectrum. 360° thermal cameras are usually only used in static environments by rotating a single camera. The prototype observes full 360° at all times, similarly the RGB imagery is available for a full 360° field of view.
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	The system is unique and rugged, such that it can be deployed in one or the other way in outdoor environments.
Product/Service Market Size	~50M€
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Non-existent: customers are not yet buying such products
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Thermal Seek, FLIR, panorama camera manufacturers, otherwise non-existent concerning this proposition
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Partnership with early adopters with particular requirements, several interested companies
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Licensing and funding of further collaborative research projects
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~200k€ annually
Expected Market Take-up	10%

3.3.5 Result ID-05: Remote Driving Experience with prototypical remote-controlled vehicle and VR integration

KER 05 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-05
Short Title of the KER	Remote Driving Experience with prototypical remote-controlled vehicle and VR integration
In depth description of the Result	A prototype of a remote-controlled vehicle equipped with an omnidirectional camera, odometry and steering sensors, a steering wheel and pedals, and a prototypical interior of a vehicle, which is used in VR to convey the experience
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Hardware Blueprint and rugged Prototype for further research and development
Market Sector addressed	Autonomous Inspection, Disaster Scenario Management
Target Customer/User addressed	HMI OEMs, System integrators, Companies working on Disaster Control and Automatic Inspection
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations,	ethical approval for user studies

compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. ~1M€
Time to Market	Two to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Current setups include one camera with a predefined field of view, and do not allow for full VR immersion; moreover, depth perception is hampered by using monocular video, and latency of control and video transmission is not state of the art
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	The versatile prototype allows for further experimentation to tune to different scenarios and to develop disaster rescue, or autonomous inspection vehicles with drivers being fully immersed in VR;
Product/Service Market Size	~50M€
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Non-existent: customers are not yet buying such products
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Non-existent concerning this proposition
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Partnership with early adopters with particular requirements, several interested companies
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Licensing and funding of further collaborative research projects, 200k/yr
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~200k€ annually
Expected Market Take-up	20%

3.3.6 Result ID-06: Algorithms and Methods for Infrastructure Visualization outdoors by way of AR

KER 06 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-06
Short Title of the KER	Algorithms and Methods for Infrastructure Visualization outdoors by way of AR
In depth description of the Result	A collection of methods and prototypes for infrastructure visualization as 3D reconstructions of excavations, pipe and line models, as well as approaches for verification and annotation

Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Software Blueprint and prototypes for further research and development
Market Sector addressed	Infrastructure, Construction, Off-highway ad-hoc installations
Target Customer/User addressed	System Integrators, Infrastructure Providers, Construction companies
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	potentially some ISO certifications
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. ~300k€
Time to Market	Two to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Paper plans do not provide in depth understanding of the situation concerning infrastructure buried underground; the prototypes and algorithms paired with accurate outdoor localization by way of Differential GPS enable this.
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	Products regarding infrastructure visualization and annotation exist sparsely in Scandinavia and Australia; companies using this mainly come from Asia
Product/Service Market Size	~50M€
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Emerging: there is growing demand, and few offerings are available
Competition	Patchy, no major players
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	e.g. BeforeUDig (NZ)
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Partnership with early adopters with particular requirements, several interested companies
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Licensing and funding of further collaborative research projects, 200k/yr
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~200k€ annually
Expected Market Take-up	20%

3.3.7 Result ID-07: Design Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Off-Highway Machinery Domain

KER ID	ID-07
Short Title of the KER	Design Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Off-Highway Machinery Domain
In depth description of the Result	Based on the result of the project we created and validated a set of Design Guidelines, dedicated to the domain of Off-Highway Machinery, which can be used for guiding the design of future XR implementation in the domain with possible extension to the broader area of Industrial Machinery. The Guidelines should be incorporated into educational programs in responsible XR development, Digital Ethics and User-Centred Security Design and become input to larger EU initiatives on XR safety, security and ethics.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Contract-based work and consulting for the ethical design of XR implementations for Off-Highway Machinery domain, educational modulus for educational projects in ethical XR
Market Sector addressed	Off-Highway Machinery (including, but not limited to the use cases of the project), broader educational sector (courses/modulus in industrial xr design education)
Target Customer/User addressed	XR designers, educators, legal scholars, human-computer interaction scholars
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	none
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	none
Time to Market	Immediately
Problems addressed and current solutions	Domain-specific Guidelines for human-centred privacy and ethics in XR implementations for Off-Highway machinery. The current solutions for describing the landscape of Design Guidelines for privacy and ethics is not considering the specific features of domain, therefore the presented Guidelines are the first one, validated with both interna projects developers, stakeholders input and broader discussion within XR community.
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	First domain-oriented ethical XR Guidelines, compatible with ISO and XRSI initiatives
Product/Service Market Size	Large, including OEMs, vehicle manufactures, external implementations providers, educational centres
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Emerging: there is growing demand, and few offerings are available
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Other Universities and consultansies, other public guidelines for privacy (XRSI) and ethics (XR4Humans) Guidelines. ISO standards in privacy (e.g. 29100)

Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Off-highway OEMs and vehicle manufacturers, broader XR design communities, professional XR ethics associations (e.g. Metaverse Standard Forum)
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Designers, Privacy and Ethics experts
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Incomes from training programs, consultancy services
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	Personal Costs
Expected Market Take-up	Immediate interest through established collaborations

3.3.8 Result ID-08: Transdisciplinary co-design approach for technical research and innovation projects

KER 08 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-08
Short Title of the KER	Transdisciplinary co-design approach for technical research and innovation projects
In depth description of the Result	Over the course of the project, a new type of participatory design and development approach specifically for technical research and innovation projects has been assembled and tested. The approach is designed to allow for a human-centric and participatory design procedure while still respecting specific technology innovation aims and technical partner expertise. The application of this approach has resulted in an in-depth knowledge and documentation of working procedures, work environment hazards and operator-approved innovative function, information and interaction concepts for XR and digital interface technologies in vehicle cabins of the respective use cases.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	University lectures, enterprise consulting services
Market Sector addressed	Education, software and/or hardware development
Target Customer/User addressed	Students, enterprises
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	None, but consultation of standard ISO 9241-210 and research ethics guidelines (e. g., SIENNA) recommended for applying the approach
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Further scientific validation and documentation
Time to Market	Immediate

Problems addressed and current solutions	Frequent incompatibility of human-centric and technology-centric research and innovation approaches, technology innovation/novelty versus acceptability. Co-design/participatory design as a process is a solution, but has only been applied in a few sectors, not yet in industrial engineering and innovation.
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	The first systematic co-design approach known to be developed specifically for engineering-based, technology-centred research and innovation projects
Product/Service Market Size	Possibly very large, all major technology-developing enterprises engaging in research and innovation projects may be targeted
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Emerging: there is growing demand, and few offerings are available
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Other universities and consulting agencies
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Off-highway OEMs and vehicle manufacturers
External Experts/Partners to be involved	None
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Income from consulting projects, third-party funded research and innovation projects
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	Personal costs only
Expected Market Take-up	Initially hesitant take-up, increasing adoption as further research and exploitation progress

3.3.9 Result ID-09: Validated, end-user-approved XR/digital interface function, information and interaction concepts for off-highway vehicle cabins

KER 09 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-09
Short Title of the KER	Validated, end-user-approved XR/digital interface function, information and interaction concepts for off-highway vehicle cabins
In depth description of the Result	Based on the novel transdisciplinary co-design approach used in the project, a set of function, information and interaction concepts for XR and digital interface technologies in off-highway vehicle cabins was developed. These concepts are presented in the form of narrative scenarios with complementary visualizations, which allow virtually any stakeholders and members of society to understand otherwise complex and domain-specific challenges and solutions. The concepts were developed for the project use cases but may be applicable or provide guidance for the innovation and design of vehicle cabin technology in other domains as well, e. g., agriculture, mining, forestry, other logistics and construction vehicles not explicitly targeted within the project.

Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Enterprise consulting services, collaboration and contract-based work in externally funded projects
Market Sector addressed	Construction, logistics, agriculture, mining, forestry
Target Customer/User addressed	Off-highway OEMs and vehicle manufacturers
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	None
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	None
Time to Market	Immediately
Problems addressed and current solutions	Domain-specific productivity and safety problems for vehicle operators; current solutions are mainly proprietary combinations of hardware and software not making use of XR technology and to our knowledge not designed in a participatory, human-centred way, leading to less-than-ideal usability and user acceptance, as has become evident in the user research phase of the project.
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	The first open-access use-case-relevant concepts developed in a co-design approach directly involving operators in design and development decisions.
Product/Service Market Size	Large, many off-highway vehicle manufacturers and OEMs from various domains may be targeted.
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Emerging: there is growing demand, and few offerings are available
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Other universities and consulting agencies
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Off-highway OEMs and vehicle manufacturers
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Privacy and legal experts
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Income from consulting projects, third-party funded research and innovation projects
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	Personal costs only
Expected Market Take-up	Immediate interest expected, as first talks with external companies have already taken place during the project

3.3.10 Result ID-10: AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept

KER 10 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-10
Short Title of the KER	AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept
In depth description of the Result	The AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept integrates advanced technologies such as real-time people tracking, 360° video feeds, and augmented reality (AR) overlays. These components were meticulously refined in both laboratory and extended reality (XR) environments to ensure a smooth transition to real-world machinery operations. The system significantly improves situational awareness by making personnel visible even when physically occluded, and by providing contextual AR cues that support rapid and informed decision-making. During field deployment, the system required minimal adjustments, demonstrating its robustness and adaptability. Remote operators quickly embraced the solution thanks to its intuitive user interface and features that actively enhance operational safety.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Consulting service, proof-of-concept, UI and concept design
Market Sector addressed	Off-Highway Machinery Segment
Target Customer/User addressed	Off-Highway OEMs, System integrators
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	GDPR (people tracking)
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	additional investment of approx. 759k€
Time to Market	two up to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	AR content to 360 video feed for better situation awareness and safety
Product/Service Market Size	
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Emerging: there is growing demand, and few offerings are available
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation

Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	market leader with turn-key solutions (e.g. NOKIA)
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Off-Highway OEMS (e.g., Sandvik, KoneKranes,)
External Experts/Partners to be involved	None
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	5M€+
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	10M€+
Expected Market Take-up	100M€+

3.3.11 Result ID-11: Snow groomer operator training simulator

KER 11 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-11
Short Title of the KER	Snow groomer operator training simulator
In depth description of the Result	A training simulator is a proven and cost-effective tool to train new operators and also to introduce new machine features or work methods for experienced operators. Creanex has developed a first operational version of the snow groomer simulation as one of the results of use case.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	A simulator for training snow groomer operators. The final product can have two different models. The light version can be a kind of suitcase version having laptop computer and the controls are mounted on the edge of an office table. The high-end version could have a seat mounted on a motion platform.
Market Sector addressed	Training, post-sales support and marketing
Target Customer/User addressed	End customers and dealers of the snow groomers
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	None
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Less than 100k. Most of the software development work is done. Additional training features must be implemented, and hardware setups need to be constructed.
Time to Market	one year
Problems addressed and current solutions	Training of operators cost effectively, post-sales support and marketing

Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	Creanex snow groomer simulator can be controlled with the actual control devices of the real snow groomer. The simulated snow groomer very closely matches the real-world version: the dimensions of its parts, its visual look, and the skiing slope terrain are the same. The snow groomer machine is modelled after Prinoth Leitwolf. The training software analyses the quality of the work was the designated driving path followed, is the snow height at the targeted levels
Product/Service Market Size	1M - 5M € or 100-500 simulators. very rough estimate
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Simulator technology is progressing both visually and functionally. Use of simulator is becoming more common, and customers are willing to accept simulator as an addition to real machine. As the amount of technology within the machine increases and its operation becomes more complex, the need for training also increases. Training with the simulator is more environmentally friendly compared to using gas powered machines.
Competition	No other snow groomer simulator available at the market. Plenty of other companies develop simulators for training, but none have snow groomer simulator.
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	None
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Schools training operators. Many schools are already using simulators for other machines and know how to utilise simulators in the education of operators.
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Creanex Oy and Prinoth AG
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Selling a simulator system with hardware and software included with a one-time payment.
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	Hardware for simulator would cost 10k-30k per unit depending on setup.
Expected Market Take-up	25% - 50%

3.3.12 Result ID-12: Haptic track controls unit

KER 12 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-12
Short Title of the KER	Haptic track controls unit
In depth description of the Result	Dual-lever unit for driving tracked vehicles, featuring direct-driven force-feedback levers and independent vibration feedback in the lever heads. The device consists of the lever pair and armrest mount, low-level force and vibrotactile feedback controllers and standard bus/network interface for communication with a high-level vehicle controller.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Track controls unit (Product, Hardware)
Market Sector addressed	Off-highway machinery - Snow grooming

Target Customer/User addressed	Off-Highway machinery OEMs
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	ISO 12100, ISO 13849-1 / -2, IEC 61508
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. €200k
Time to Market	two up to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Vehicle handling and navigation under difficult conditions, currently no technological solution, reliance on operator expertise
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	Capability of providing force and tactile feedback to the operator during driving
Product/Service Market Size	Approx. 390M€ (global snow groomer market)
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Emerging: there is growing demand, and few offerings are available
Competition	Patchy, no major players
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	none
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Off-Highway OEMS (e.g., Prinoth)
External Experts/Partners to be involved	none
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Technology licensing, components sales, ~500k€ annually
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~300k€ annually
Expected Market Take-up	25%

3.3.13 Result ID-13: Vibrotactile handle concept for force-feedback devices

KER 13 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-13
Short Title of the KER	Vibrotactile handle concept for force-feedback devices
In depth description of the Result	Custom handle for force-feedback devices incorporating a vibrotactile actuator with a custom mechanical mount ensuring optimal vibration cue perception, along with electronics controller architecture for triggering cues.

Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Vibrotactile handle (Product, hardware), driving software (Product, software)
Market Sector addressed	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Haptic Devices
Target Customer/User addressed	HMI OEMs, System integrators
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	ISO 12100, ISO 13849-1 / -2, ISO 9355-1, EN 60204-1, ISO 13849-1
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. 100k€-200k€
Time to Market	one to two years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Unimodal haptics in force-feedback device handle, no current solution
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	Capability of providing combined force and tactile feedback in a haptic HMI device
Product/Service Market Size	~5M€
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Non-existent: customers are not yet buying such products
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Force feedback devices: Force Dimension (CH), Haply (CA/FR)
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Robotics integrators, Haption customer base
External Experts/Partners to be involved	None
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Components sales, software licensing ~50k€ annually
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~25k€ annually
Expected Market Take-up	30%

3.3.14 Result ID-14: 6-axis haptic arm for use in demanding environments

KER 14 - Exploitation Strategy and BM

KER ID	ID-14
Short Title of the KER	6-axis haptic arm for use in demanding environments
In depth description of the Result	A serial-linkage 6 degree-of-freedom force-feedback haptic device designed specifically for use in demanding environments, with its associated low-level controller
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	6DoF force feedback device for demanding environments
Market Sector addressed	Human-machine interfaces (HMI), Haptic Devices
Target Customer/User addressed	HMI OEMs, System integrators
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	ISO9001
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. ~1M€
Time to Market	Two to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Desktop haptic devices are generally not robust to harsh use conditions (temperature, pollution, shocks and vibration)
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	The novel haptic arm provides high force and torque feedback, in a compact form factor, with a design ensuring robustness to harsh environments
Product/Service Market Size	~6M€
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Non-existent: customers are not yet buying such products
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Force Dimension (CH), Haply (CA/FR)
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	
External Experts/Partners to be involved	None
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Device sales, ~500k€ annually
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~200k€ annually
Expected Market Take-up	20%

3.3.15 Result ID-15: Software bridge for interfacing 3rd party simulators and game engines with Haption force-feedback devices

KER 15 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-15
Short Title of the KER	Software bridge for interfacing 3rd party simulators and game engines with Haption force-feedback devices
In depth description of the Result	A software component providing a high-level standard interface for controlling the pose of components and retrieving standard haptic constraints from 3rd party simulators or game engines. The software allows rapid prototyping of common force-feedback interaction scenarios with virtual environments, without requiring in-depth design of haptic behaviors.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Software bridge (Product, software)
Market Sector addressed	Simulators, game engines
Target Customer/User addressed	End-users of Haption force-feedback devices, System integrators
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	ISO 25010
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Negligible additional investments required
Time to Market	one to two years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Low-level API for force feedback devices requires users to spend significant time designing haptic constraints
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	The software enables a trade-off of flexibility provided by our low-level API for ease of development and speed of implementation for applications involving standard haptic constraints in virtual environments
Product/Service Market Size	n.a.
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Mature: the market is already supplied with many products of the type proposed
Competition	Several major players with strong competencies and infrastructure
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Force-feedback device and solution providers: Force Dimension (CH), 3DSystems (US), Haply (CA/FR); Open-source solutions: CHAI3D, SOFA, ForceHost
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	

External Experts/Partners to be involved	n.a.
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	No direct revenues, potential for indirect revenue through stimulation of haptic input device adoption
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	n.a.
Expected Market Take-up	n.a.

3.3.16 Result ID-16: Force and tactile assistance function concepts for off-highway vehicles

KER 16 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-16
Short Title of the KER	Force and tactile assistance function concepts for off-highway vehicles
In depth description of the Result	Set of concepts and prototype implementations of haptic assistance functions (tactile and force feedback)
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Firmware / Software implementing haptic assistance functions
Market Sector addressed	Off-highway vehicles
Target Customer/User addressed	Off-highway vehicle OEMs
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	ISO 13849, IEC 61508, ISO 9001
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. €200k
Time to Market	two up to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	Vehicle handling and navigation under difficult conditions, Vehicle tool handling under difficult conditions, currently no technological solution, reliance on operator expertise
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	Capability of providing assistive force and tactile feedback to the operator during driving and tool handling
Product/Service Market Size	Approx. 390M€ (global snow groomer market)
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Non-existent: customers are not yet buying such products

Competition	Patchy, no major players
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	none
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Off-Highway OEMS (e.g., Prinoth)
External Experts/Partners to be involved	none
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Software licensing, patent leasing, ~100k€-200k€ annually
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~50k€ annually
Expected Market Take-up	25%

3.3.17 Result ID-17: AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept

KER 17 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-17
Short Title of the KER	AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept
In depth description of the Result	<p>The AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept integrates advanced technologies such as real-time people tracking, 360° video feeds, and augmented reality (AR) overlays. These components were meticulously refined in both laboratory and extended reality (XR) environments to ensure a smooth transition to real-world machinery operations in port and terminal environments.</p> <p>The system significantly improves situational awareness by making personnel visible even when physically occluded, and by providing contextual AR cues that support rapid and informed decision-making. During field deployment, the system required minimal adjustments, demonstrating its robustness and adaptability. Remote operators quickly embraced the solution thanks to its intuitive user interface and features that actively enhance operational safety.</p>
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Novel AR-Enhanced Operator Terminal/UI
Market Sector addressed	Off-Highway cargo handling Machinery Segment
Target Customer/User addressed	Off-Highway OEMs, System integrators like Kalmar
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	GDPR (people tracking)

Cost to bring product/service to the “market” (before actual Exploitation)	Additional investment of approx. 789k€
Time to Market	From two up to three years
Problems addressed and current solutions	High component prices at the moment
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	AR content to 360 video feed for better situation awareness and safety
Product/Service Market Size	About 5 M€ annually
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	Emerging: there is growing demand, and few offerings are available
Competition	Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	Market leader with turn-key solutions (e.g. NOKIA)
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	Global terminal operators
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Existing partner network
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	5M€+
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	8M€+
Expected Market Take-up	100M€+

3.3.18 Result ID-18: Snow groomer simulator

KER 18 - Exploitation Strategy and BM	
KER ID	ID-18
Short Title of the KER	Snow groomer simulator
In depth description of the Result	A snow grooming simulator exists of an operator cabin with original controls and a simulation software which allows to move and control a snow groomer in a digital world. This provides a possibility to get common with the controls of a snow groomer without sitting in a snow groomer.
Product/Service that will be offered based on the result	Training simulator with or without motion platform

Market Sector addressed	Training of new operator, pre-sales support, gamification
Target Customer/User addressed	Ski resorts and/or sales structure
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	EN10029
Cost to bring product/service to the "market" (before actual Exploitation)	~3M€ Basic controls are working, full integration required. Vehicle behaviour needs to be finetuned, tiller finish required. Specific behaviour for each model, accessory and application required.
Time to Market	3 years
Problems addressed and current solutions	snow grooming is a seasonal business - with the simulator you can provide trainings at any time
Differentiators and Unique Selling Point	Simulation of your ski resort. Operate the snow groomer with original controls and behaviour.
Product/Service Market Size	~50 simulators (just big resort might think on investing in a simulator)
Market Trends/Maturity/Acceptance	High staff turnover and many career changer work as snow groomer operator. The acceptance of training possibilities is not yet widespread and accepted.
Competition	not existing/ just some enthusiast trying to build their own simulator. Winter simulator has a snow groomer in his Game.
Competitors/Incumbents (type/company names)	-
Early Adopters - First Customers (type/company names)	big conglomerates
External Experts/Partners to be involved	Creanex, TTC
Expected Revenues Models and Flows	Sell Training on Simulator base/ rent the simulator/ sell the simulator
Expected Resources needs and Costs Structure	~ 100k€/Year
Expected Market Take-up	~ 150k€/year

4 Risk Assessment of Exploitable Results

4.1 Summary and Major Findings

The THEIA^{XR} result owners compiled a risk self-assessment of their own exploitable results in the project. The summary of this activity is given in the following subsections on the individual basis as well as on a compiled basis to provide an overview for project itself.

The method used for this assessment can be briefly described as follows. Each result owner was asked to identify and list all risks associated with the exploitation of their result and map them into six pre-defined categories. For every identified risk they were asked to assign a degree of importance (on a scale from one to ten) as well as the probability of occurrence (on a scale from one to ten). The product of these two values defines a risk grade. To determine the potential for mitigating the risk from the owner's perspective, an additional parameter was assessed, namely the scope and type of potential intervention. The foreseen potential of the risk mitigation measure was then rated between one (low success of intervention) and ten (high success of intervention). The risk grade and the feasibility of the risk mitigation measure define two dimensions to visualise all six categories in a scatter plot shown in Figure 28. The six categories have been pre-defined to structure the outcome of this assessment and cover a broader spectrum in terms of exploitation and impact creation. The following risk types or classes were selected beforehand:

- Partnership Risk Factors – including all stakeholder during the exploitation process.
- Technological Risk Factors – emerging from the technological and scientific development.
- Market Risk Factors – considering the target market.
- IPR/Legal Risk Factors – emerging from IP protection as well as legal frameworks.
- Financial/Management Risk Factors – emerging from necessary additional investments until market launch-
- Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors which might occur from governmental stakeholders and/or the society.

Figure 28 depicts the summary of the assessment for all risk categories and intends to provide an indication of the risk awareness of the consortium when it comes to exploitation activities. The score is calculated like the individual risk assessment per exploitable result by combining all risks mentioned for a predefined category. The plot is divided into four quadrants where each defines the significance of the assessed parameters. A risk grade below 50 in combination with a success factor for interventions below 5 indicates an area of no immediate activity (no-action) or intervention for risk falling into the respective category. Similar interpretations can be derived for the rest of the quadrants.

Figure 28 shows that all six categories fall into the area where the risk grade is below 50 and the high probability of a successful risk mitigation measure can be achieved. Given the fact that most exploitable results are still in a prototypical stage (TRL 5-6), it highlights the potential of the technical achievements towards a market ready product or service. Since THEIA^{XR} is classified as research and innovation action (RIA) the findings demonstrate the awareness of the project participants concerning barriers and potential hazards when it comes to driving the innovations towards a successful market entry. Furthermore, the exercise supports individual result owners to trigger further public or private investments to achieve the necessary market maturity. It is worth mentioning that most risks have been identified around technological risks, partnership risks, and market risks. Result owners related to the three use-case in the project reported the more risk in the categories market risk factors and partnership risk. The latter mostly refers to supply chain risks estimated for those KERs which include hardware like chips and other components, when looking on the individual data provided.

Figure 28: Overall Project Risk Assessment

The individual findings on an individual key exploitable result basis are listed in the subsection below.

4.2 Risk Assessment of individual Results

4.2.1 Result ID-01: High performance computing platform for the execution of algorithms/applications

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution (Please edit)	Degree of importance of the risk Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention Please edit	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	7	4			6	
Production Process delay due to supplier shortage	5	2	26	Diversification of Supply Chain	8	156
Semiconductor supply chain shortage for the edge hardware platform	8	6		Observation of alternative suppliers for simple components and main SoC's	4	
Technological Risk Factors	6	7			6	
Novel more computational advanced technologies endanger hardware product ECU lifecycle	8	8	42	Agile analysis of customer use-cases to assess market demand for even more powerful ECUs	5	231
Development toolchain too complex for target market	4	6		Provide development services and trainings for market participants	6	
Market Risk Factors	6	7			8	
Customer do not adapt for the mobile computing solution	6	7	42	Proper Market Analysis / Use-Cases with Lead Customers	8	336
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	5			5	
Earlier patent by competitor in the targetted area of use	5	5	25	IPR management and monitoring	5	125
Financial/management Risk Factors	8	4			7	
ECU and software framework maturity not in synch, e.g. toolchain not ready at product launch	8	4	32	Proper Milestone planning and monitoring	7	224
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	7			7	
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	7	7	53	Proper monitoring standardization activities	8	368
Compliance obligations (e.g., Cybersecurity Act, AI Act, etc.) increases developments and Life Cycle Management costs	8	7		Monitoring and alignment with best practice examples from the off-highway market	6	

4.2.2 Result ID-02: Multimodal Cabin Mock-Up

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	9	5			6		
Industrialization / Commercialisation at risk: no manufacturer /service provider to use the exploitable result.	9	5	45	targeted marketing for potential customers	6	270	
Technological Risk Factors	7	2			5		
Technical complexity	7	2	14	prioritisation of new features to be developed	5	63	
					reduction of complexits		4
Market Risk Factors	8	3			6		
Nobody buys the product. Rejected by end-users.	8	3	24	business model concepts to lower the barrier to test product	6	144	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	4	2			4		
Know- how risks: it is easy to counterfeit the patent.	4	2	8	legal and contractual safeguarding, licensing	3	35	
					code and hardware obfuscation		4
					strategic positioning and branding		6
Financial/management Risk Factors	3	3			3		
Lack of endorsement from top management	3	3	9		3	27	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	3	1			6		
Influence of laws and regulations.	3	1	3	compliance framework and internal controls	6	18	

4.2.3 Result ID-03: Laser and DLP Projection System for Outdoor Projective Augmented Reality

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low-10 high)</small>	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	5	3			8		
No suitable partners for further development/research	5	3	15	Public Dissemination Activities	8	120	
Technological Risk Factors	5	5			9		
Design constraints hampering adoption	5	5	25	Restriction of feature sets	9	225	
Market Risk Factors	6	8			8		
Benefit is not understood and valued high enough	6	8	48	Proper use-case analysis with Lead Customers	8	384	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	3			7		
Competitor patent in target area	5	3	15	IPR management and monitoring	7	105	
Financial/management Risk Factors	3	3			9		
Miniaturization costs exceed planned budgets	3	3	9	proper planning and selection of components	9	81	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	3			10		
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	3	24	Proper monitoring of standards	10	240	

4.2.4 Result ID-04: Panoramic 360° Thermal Camera with 360° RGB Images

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	8	8			8		
No suitable partners for further development/research	8	8	64	Public Dissemination Activities	8	512	
Technological Risk Factors	7	3			7		
Design constraints hampering adoption in machinery	7	3	21	Restriction of feature sets	7	147	
Market Risk Factors	10	2			8		
Cost factors	10	2	20	Suitable component selection	8	160	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	3			7		
Competitor patent in target area	5	3	15	IPR management and monitoring	7	105	
Financial/management Risk Factors	10	5			8		
No investment in research	10	5	50	Proper cross-funding of developments	8	400	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	3			10		
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	3	24	Proper monitoring of standards	10	240	

4.2.5 Result ID-05: Remote Driving Experience with prototypical remote controlled vehicle and VR integration

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low-10 high)</small>	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	7	9			10		
Failure to find partners willing to enter the journey	7	9	63	Proper proposal and clear communication and dissemination activities	10	630	
Technological Risk Factors	5	3			6		
Network providers don't provide sufficient bandwidth	5	3	15	Software-based compression algorithms	6	90	
Market Risk Factors	5	3			8		
Products do not meet price point	5	3	15	Proper use of hardware components to lower cost	8	120	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	1			7		
Competitor patent in target area	5	1	5	IPR management and monitoring	7	35	
Financial/management Risk Factors	4	3			9		
Lead customers do not invest enough money	4	3	12	Proper value proposition, testing and demonstration	9	108	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	3			10		
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	3	24	Proper monitoring of standards	10	240	

4.2.6 Result ID-06: Algorithms and Methods for Infrastructure Visualization outdoors by way of AR

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low-10 high)</small>	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	8	7			8		
Partners do not understand proposition	8	7	56	Communicate and disseminate by examples	8	448	
Technological Risk Factors	8	9			6		
Infrastructure is not available as digital assets	8	9	72	Developing Adapters and Educated companies	6	432	
Market Risk Factors	4	8			8		
Use Cases cannot be monetized by companies	4	8	32	Proper use-case analysis with Lead Customers	8	256	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	2			7		
Competitor patent in target area	5	2	10	IPR management and monitoring	7	70	
Financial/management Risk Factors	3	6			9		
Companies don't want to invest and be early movers	3	6	18	Dissimination activities, education and training	9	162	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	3			10		
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	3	24	Proper monitoring of standards	10	240	

4.2.7 Result ID-07: Design Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Off-Highway Machinery Domain

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low-10 high)</small>	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	8	5			9	
The Design Guidelines can affect the profitability of companies solutions and restrict the data gathering, therefore companies will less likely to adopt them	8	5	40	As the Guidelines are designed in line with major EU directions on privacy (e.g. GDPR) and the Human Rights paradigm, the following the Guidelines will help companies increase the compliance and maintain ethical profile in front of competitors; we also expecting the key EU XR ethics and safety initiatives will promote our approach to the design	9	360
Technological Risk Factors	8	7			9	
Some Guidelines (e.g. Guidelines related to AI) can be difficult to implement in current SoA of AI, and it is generally difficult to prove to which extent the companies follow the Guidelines during the implementation as they are high-leveled	8	7	56	The technology-holders (UL) can provide training and assesement on Guidelines implementation	9	504
Market Risk Factors	5	7			9	
Companies prefer to design their own Design Guidelines instead of applying the developed Guidelines	5	7	35	Work on promoting the Guidelines as part of the EU XR development standards, participate in the open-discussions with public and industry representatives	9	315
IPR/legal Risk Factors	2	2			9	
Guidelines are not compatible with foreign privacy regulations	2	2	4	As we currently observe the tendency of unifying the privacy legislations across the globe under EU model (so-called "Brussels Effect"), the legislative difference should not prevent the Guidelines implementation	9	36
Financial/management Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
not applicable			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
not applicable			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!

4.2.8 Result ID-08: Transdisciplinary co-design approach for technical research and innovation projects

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution (Please edit)	Degree of importance of the risk Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention Please edit	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	9	7			7	
The co-design team may be lacking decision power, exchange opportunities with involved partners, or support from required partners (e.g. technical partners)	8	7	59	Clear agreement and regular consultations on responsibilities, transparent communication of aims and results of co-design towards partners	6	410
Co-design team cannot get timely and reliable access to essential end-users or stakeholders needed, which severely increases the effort and budget needed	10	6		Dependencies on specific end-user and stakeholder groups must be clarified before the start of the project, participant recruitment plans and budget must be prepared	8	
Technological Risk Factors	8	4			8	
Co-design team cannot sufficiently understand complex technologies involved.	8	4	32	Include technical experts in the co-design team. Conduct internal trainings beforehand.	8	256
Market Risk Factors	8	7			5	
Enterprises may not be willing to commit to this kind of approach in a research and innovation project	8	7	56	Expected outcomes, risks and advantages of this approach must be communicated clearly and scientifically validated, if possible	5	280
IPR/legal Risk Factors	8	7			7	
Incorrect collection and handling of sensitive participant data	8	7	56	Development and adherence of a data management plan. Raise awareness for proper data handling in the co-design team.	7	392
Financial/management Risk Factors	7	6			7	
Design and development decisions may not be possible to make based on insufficient or ambiguous end-user and stakeholder feedback	4	7	38	A co-design process manager or managing committee can be established to make informed decisions in unclear situations	8	277
Participant recruitment and involvement required for successful application of the approach may exceed allocated financial and time budget, which may in turn cause personal costs for involved co-design managers/moderators to rise	7	5		A realistic participant recruitment and involvement plan allowing for minor delays and specific guidelines for how to act in case of unforeseen delays must be developed	7	
Management overrides decisions made in the co-design team	9	5		Include management from the beginning of the project. Raise awareness for consequences of top-down decisions.	7	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	6	6			8	
Concepts resulting from the co-design process may be incompatible with laws and regulations.	6	6	36	Involve experts for laws and regulations in the co-design process. Explore alternatives for potentially incompatible concepts.	8	288

4.2.9 Result ID-09: Validated, end-user-approved XR/digital interface function, information and interaction concepts for off-highway vehicle cabins

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution (Please edit)	Degree of importance of the risk Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention Please edit	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	8	6			8	
Companies cannot get timely and reliable access to essential end-users or stakeholders needed in order to validate and adapt concept solutions to their own domain and end-user requirements.	8	6	48	Dependencies on specific end-user and stakeholder groups must be clarified before the start of the project, participant recruitment plans and budget must be prepared.	8	384
Technological Risk Factors	8	5			6	
The concepts cannot be implemented cost-efficiently.	8	5	40	Development of prototypes and proof of concepts as a first step before the final implementation. Honest and transparent communication about feasibility of the concepts.	6	240
Market Risk Factors	8	7			5	
Enterprises may not be willing to use the scenarios and the XR and interface concepts	8	7	56	Make results known in the community, communicate the benefits clearly.	5	280
IPR/legal Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
None			#DIV/0!	None		#DIV/0!
Financial/management Risk Factors	8	4			7	
Attempting to use and implement the concepts directly in a different domain without further validation efforts may cause user acceptance issues and result in failure of the project.	8	4	32	Use-case-specific context of developed concepts must be clarified, need for domain-specific adaptation and validation of concepts must be emphasized.	7	224
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	6	6			8	
Some concepts may be incompatible with laws and regulations in specific countries or domains.	6	6	36	Involve experts for laws and regulations in the co-design process. Explore alternatives for potentially incompatible concepts.	8	288

4.2.10 Result ID-10: AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	3	3			7		
Disagreement on ownership rules	3	3	9	Using open source components in SW	7	63	
Technological Risk Factors	5	6			6		
Development toolchain too complex for target market	5	6	30	Provide development services and trainings for market participants	6	180	
Market Risk Factors	5	5			8		
Nobody buys the product. Rejected by end-users.	5	5	25	Proper Market Analysis / Use-Cases with Lead Customers and end-user interviews	8	200	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	5			5		
Earlier patent by competitor in the targetted area of use	5	5	25	IPR management and monitoring	5	125	
Financial/management Risk Factors	8	4			7		
Lack of endorsement from top management	8	4	32	Proper Milestone planning and monitoring	7	224	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	7			7		
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	7	56	Proper monitoring standardization activities especially in XR domain	7	392	

4.2.11 Result ID-11: Snow groomer operator training simulator

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution (Please edit)	Degree of importance of the risk Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention Please edit	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	3	2			8		
Prinoh stops supporting simulator development. One of our current selling points is that the machine is very close to a commonly used real machine, with exactly the same control systems.	3	2	6	Change snowgroomer model to generic unbranded one	8	48	
Technological Risk Factors	6	4			6		
The simulated behaviour of the machine and snow is unrealistic or too different from the real machine, so training is less useful.	6	4	24	Use better hardware to enable better physics simulation. Invest in fixing problematic aspects.	6	144	
Market Risk Factors	7	6			4		
Simulator is too expensive for customers	8	8	39	Try to sell many units so software development costs per unit are low. Only implement necessary features. Use simpler and cheaper hardware where possible	2	137	
Competitors develop snow groomer simulator	5	4			Investigate in which areas they are better, and see if we can respond there. Use our strengths as selling points.		5
IPR/legal Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!		
			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
Financial/management Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!		
			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	5	3			5		
Climate change reduces need for snow groomers. Even a small decline in future demand for snow groomers can make customers wary of investments to new technology.	5	3	15	Gain a foothold in education institutions and dealers sooner than later.	5	75	

4.2.12 Result ID-12: Haptic track controls unit

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution (Please edit)	Degree of importance of the risk Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention Please edit	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	5	3			8		
Supplier parts shortage	5	3	15	Diversification of supply chain	8	120	
Technological Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!		
			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
Market Risk Factors	7	6			8		
Customers do not adapt to novel feedback modality	5	7	39	Proper Market Analysis / Use-Cases with Lead Customers	8	312	
Device cost exceeds perceived customer benefit	8	5			Proper use-case analysis with Lead Customers		8
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	3			7		
Competitor patent in target area	5	3	15	IPR management and monitoring	7	105	
Financial/management Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!		
			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	3			10		
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	3	24	Proper monitoring of standards	10	240	

4.2.13 Result ID-13: Vibrotactile handle concept for force-feedback devices

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	7	3			6		
Supplier parts shortage	7	3	21	Diversification of supply chain	6	126	
Technological Risk Factors	7	3			8		
Emergence of higher quality tactile feedback actuators	7	3	21	Proper monitoring of state of the art	8	168	
Market Risk Factors	5	5			8		
Customers do not adapt to novel feedback modality	5	5	25	Proper Market Analysis / Use-Cases with Lead Customers	8	200	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	8	2			7		
Competitor patent in target area	8	2	16	IPR management and monitoring	7	112	
Financial/management Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!		
			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	2			10		
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	2	16	Proper monitoring of standards	10	160	

4.2.14 Result ID-14: 6-axis haptic arm for use in demanding environments

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	5	3			8		
Supplier parts shortage	5	3	15	Diversification of supply chain	8	120	
Technological Risk Factors	5	5			6		
Haptics quality is degraded due to design constraints	5	5	25	Software compensation	6	150	
Market Risk Factors	5	7			8		
Use-cases do not actualize	5	7	35	Proper use-case analysis with Lead Customers	8	280	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	3			7		
Competitor patent in target area	5	3	15	IPR management and monitoring	7	105	
Financial/management Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!		
			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	3			10		
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	3	24	Proper monitoring of standards	10	240	

4.2.15 Result ID-15: Software bridge for interfacing 3rd party simulators and game engines with Haption force-feedback devices

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low-10 high)</small>	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
Technological Risk Factors	5	3	15		8	120
Incompatibility with new emerging simulation or game engine frameworks	5	3		Monitoring of existing simulation and game engine framework offerings	8	
Market Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
IPR/legal Risk Factors	8	1	8		8	64
Competitor patent in target area	8	1		IPR management and monitoring	8	
Financial/management Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!

4.2.16 Result ID-16: Force and tactile assistance function concepts for off-highway vehicles

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low-10 high)</small>	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
Technological Risk Factors	5	3	15		8	120
Incompatibility with new emerging simulation or game engine frameworks	5	3		Monitoring of existing simulation and game engine framework offerings	8	
Market Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
IPR/legal Risk Factors	8	1	8		8	64
Competitor patent in target area	8	1		IPR management and monitoring	8	
Financial/management Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!

4.2.17 Result ID-17: AR-Enhanced Remote Operation Concept

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution <small>(Please edit)</small>	Degree of importance of the risk <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Probability of risk happening <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)</small>	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention <small>Please edit</small>	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention <small>Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)</small>	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	4	4			7	
Disagreement on ownership rules	4	4	16	Using open source components in SW with problematic license	7	112
Technological Risk Factors	5	6			6	
Development toolchain too complex / expensive for target market	5	6	30	Careful evaluation of used tools and collaboration with research partner.	6	180
Market Risk Factors	5	5			8	
Nobody buys the product. Rejected by end-users.	5	5	25	Proper global market analysis with potential customers. Analysis of the value creation for the customers.	8	200
IPR/legal Risk Factors	5	5			5	
Earlier patent by competitor in the targetted area of use	5	5	25	IPR management and monitoring	5	125
Financial/management Risk Factors	8	4			7	
Lack of endorsement from top management	8	4	32	Proper planning and monitoring by steering group meetings.	7	224
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	8	7			7	
Product/service does not comply with new emerging standards.	8	7	56	Proper monitoring standardization activities especially in XR domain.	7	392

4.2.18 Result ID-08: Snow groomer simulator

RISK FACTORS related to the final Exploitation of the developed solution (Please edit)	Degree of importance of the risk Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention Please edit	Feasibility/ Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level	
Partnership Risk Factors	8	3			9		
Creax not available for future cooperation	8	3	24	Benchmark competitor and choose another one	9	216	
Technological Risk Factors	8	6			5		
Simulation code not suitable for implementing all requirements.	8	6	48	Reuse existing code partially for implementation to best fitting solution	5	240	
Market Risk Factors	9	9			3		
Market price for rent and sale not accepted	9	9	81	reallocate training to Prinoth facilities	3	243	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!		
			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	
Financial/management Risk Factors	6	3			9		
Invest for finalization too high	6	3	18	limit to basic functions	9	162	
Environmental/Regulatory Risk Factors	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!		
			#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	

The next chapter provides an updated version of the exploitation strategy per company considering the findings and results of the I THEIA^{XR} project.

5 Exploitation Strategy

The following section provides the update of the exploitation strategies of each individual participant in the project. The section is split into two clusters namely (i) **product exploitation** and deployment strategies for industry partners and (ii) **knowledge enhancement** and community outreach for academic partners. Given the nature of those partner's major business interests or target groups and considering the exploitable results, these partners achieved during the THEIA^{XR} project, the individual strategies reflect the exploitation activities beyond the project's end.

5.1 Product Exploitation and Deployment Strategies

Partner TTC:

TTControl's exploitation plan with respect to the results within the THEIA^{XR} project is compliant with the internal company strategy of shaping the next generation of mobile machinery and providing high-performance control systems and advanced electronics for off-highway machines.

TTControl's contribution to the THEIA^{XR} project include one key result, which is an embedded, centralized and ruggedized high-performance computing platform. The result will be exploited through the product portfolio of TTControl and the network of TTControl and the parent company Hydac International GmbH, which is a world-wide company also selling TTControl products. Additionally, the results of this solution form the basis for future high-performance computing platforms, which are the core technology required for future autonomous operation of mobile machinery.

The embedded platform can be seen as an edge computer capable of handling various input and output devices, varying from sensors, virtual worlds, actuators, but also displays, force feedback control and active lighting outputs. These embedded platforms can host various applications handling the data coming from the input sources, performing (potentially AI-based) processing of the data and forwarding the data, either to the machine for operation or to the human operators providing feedback about the task at hand, environmental information, machine data, etc.

The KER ID-01 of the project will be mainly exploited through the product portfolio of TTControl and presented to our various customers at trade fairs (e.g., Agritechnica or BAUMA) or published in industrial journals. Through these networks, TTControl will raise the awareness of their solutions and target to become the market leader in embedded high performance computing platforms for off-highway mobile machinery.

The future concerning feature development is to adapt the platform to the requirements of the market and the end users, gain know-how by deploying the solution in other domains and work on scalability and ease of integration for OEMs and system integrators. TTControl will continue working on the platform, implement new functionalities, like e.g., security measures and support for new applications (e.g., AI based data processing), so that the future products will be ready for the market.

Partner CREA:

Creanex is a company that makes simulators of mobile work machines for operator training, research and development, and testing. Creanex has been participating in the UC1 snow groomer and UC3 excavator use cases with three main exploitation goals for the project:

- Develop a snow groomer simulator for operator training. (ID01)
- Modernize and improve our excavator simulator
- Develop general improvements to our simulator platform that can be utilized in our other simulators.

In UC1 Creanex developed a snow groomer simulator. Because the simulator was used to demonstrate and evaluate technologies developed in the project, Creanex' focus was to implement simulated versions of those same technologies into the simulator.

Exploitation long term goal is to sell the simulator for Prinoth dealers, education institutions training snow groomer operators and others who have a need for training operators. A first version of the simulator was demonstrated during the InterAlpin trade fair, where several people from regional Prinoth dealers and school representatives expressed interest.

Prinoth provided Creanex with an accurate 3D model of the Leitwolf and other technical support, which enabled Creanex to develop a simulator that is very close to the real machine. The simulator uses the same control input devices as the real machine, the snow groomer blade and tiller have the same parts and movements, and the skiing slope is modelled after Ladurns skiing resort. Training the operators from the start in a realistic machine and actual skiing slope is an advantage for the simulator.

In UC3 Creanex further developed their already existing excavator simulator. Again, the focus was on implementing the technologies developed by partners, so our simulators can be used by the partners to test, evaluate and demonstrate those new technologies. When trade schools buy a training simulator package from us, an excavator simulator is often included. Many of the updates and improvements made to excavator are included in those training simulators.

Because all Creanex simulators use the same engine, much of the work can be utilised in future simulators and machines other than excavator or snow groomer. Examples of this include:

- The simulation of modifiable surfaces with loose material was improved. The pushing of snow using the snow groomer blade and digging soil with excavator bucket use the same code underneath. The results can be utilised in other similar machines, such as wheel loaders and bulldozers.
- Creanex experimented and developed their VR and XR integration capabilities. A framework for using video passthrough in VR was developed, which is useful in all simulators where VR is used, and is a feature that sets us apart from other competitors.

Partner PRIN:

Prinoth has demonstrated a strong commitment to the research outcomes and proved to safeguard key results through patent protection. During the Theia Project, Prinoth presented initial results at InterAlpin, the leading trade fair for alpine equipment in Innsbruck. This underscores not only the strategic relevance of THEIA^{XR} for Prinoth but also validates the methodological approaches adopted within the project. The developed concepts and technologies have significantly broadened the innovation horizon.

A simulation environment replicating a ski resort within an original vehicle cabin enables realistic operation of grooming machines. This system not only provides a training platform for inexperienced operators but also facilitates digital reproduction and implementation of new development steps. Such an approach reduces time and cost by requiring only a static workstation without fuel consumption.

The company has defined a strategy to advance and incorporate the most promising concepts into its production processes, contingent upon their readiness for industrialization. Prinoth expresses openness to continued collaboration with project partners. To this end, dedicated development projects have been initiated and required financial resources for the first phase are expected to be released by 2026.

THEIA^{XR}'s development approach places vehicle operators at the center, recognizing them as key stakeholders whose integration ensures user-driven solutions. This participatory method has proven highly effective. Prinoth innovation process can yield more efficient outcomes with minor adjustments. Prinoth group portfolio extends beyond snow groomers to include crawler carriers, vegetation management, and tree care solutions. Knowledge gained from THEIA^{XR} and its methodologies is being disseminated across all business units, ensuring that these insights inform future product definitions.

Partner HAP:

HAP's exploitation plan for the results obtained in the THEIA^{XR} project follows Haption's strategic ambitions as an SME standing among European market leaders in force-feedback devices, with a strong focus on innovation through academic and industrial collaboration at the European level.

HAP's contributions to the THEIA^{XR} project include five key results: (1) a first hardware device, the two-axis, force and tactile feedback-capable haptic track controls unit; (2) a second hardware device, the 6-axis haptic arm with interchangeable handle concept, designed for use in highly demanding environments; (3) vibrotactile handles for force-feedback devices; (4) a software bridge for interfacing Haption force-feedback hardware with 3rd party simulation and game engines through a standard network interface; (5) multiple force and tactile assistance function concepts for the off-highway vehicle domain.

Haption plans on exploiting these results through several commercial and non-commercial avenues. The results will be leveraged internally, through incorporation into Haption's portfolio of technological offerings or by being used as foundations for future research and development work, as well as externally, through direct collaboration with industrial partners from within the consortium, fostering Haption's collaboration with European industrial partners.

- (1) The haptic track controls unit, identified as KER ID_12, will be primarily exploited in collaboration with project partner Prinoth SA. Internal discussions are underway regarding the possibility of applying for a shared patent on the concept, following which the IPR may be either jointly exploited or licensed. Furthermore, this result will serve Haption internally, as foundation for future R&D work on bringing haptics to lever-driven systems and vehicles.
- (2) The 6-axis haptic arm with interchangeable handle concept for use in machinery operating in demanding environments, identified as KER ID_14, will primarily be exploited internally during future R&D work conducted internally or funded nationally or through future EU projects. Iterations on the prototype produced in THEIA will allow Haption to expand its product portfolio to haptic devices for use in demanding environments, moving beyond our traditional scope of static "desktop" haptics.
- (3) The vibrotactile handle concept for force-feedback devices, identified as KER ID_13, will also extend Haption's internal capabilities offering. The option will be offered to customers interested in custom combined tactile and force-feedback solutions, moving Haption beyond its traditional scope of unimodal, kinesthetic-only haptics.
- (4) The software bridge for interfacing Haption force-feedback hardware with 3rd party simulation and game engines, identified as KER ID_15, will primarily be used internally as a building block for future R&D and function demonstrations. After improvements and testing, it will be provided as a free tool for Haption's customer base to use for their own developments using Haption devices, with the aim of increasing adoption of haptics technology for interaction with virtual environments.
- (5) The force and tactile assistance function concepts for off-highway vehicles, identified as KER ID_16, will be exploited in several ways. The functions regarding snow groomer driving will be exploited in collaboration with project partner Prinoth SA along with KER ID_4 described above. Other functions will serve as foundation work for future R&D work on haptic assistance functions to be conducted internally, as well as forming a basis for applications to future public funded research programs.

These results (in particular (5)) will also be shared in demonstrations for customers (e.g. at trade fairs) or published in the relevant academic venues (haptics conferences or journals). This will contribute to increasing awareness of the transformative potential of haptic technologies (and XR technologies as a whole) for improving operator performance, comfort and safety across a diverse range of industries, accelerating

adoption of these technologies and extending the impact of research and development activities from THEIA^{XR} beyond the end of the project.

Partner KAL:

KALMAR's exploitation plan for the THEIA^{XR} project is consistent with our strategy, technology roadmap and business goals for near future.

KALMAR's strategy changed after the beginning of the THEIA^{XR} project. Kalmar decided to concentrate on manufacturing mobile heavy cargo handling machines, and we decided to stop manufacturing of cranes for terminals. We decided to change our use-case machine from remote control of RTG crane to remote control of a reach stacker. For reach stacker remote control is not widely utilized yet. Handheld devices are utilized to control the boom and spreader when visibility is limited, for example when loading the barges next to the high edge of the quay. During the project we finalized our remote-control design for reach stackers so that it is mainly utilized to help the system in those cases where automation system of the machine is not capable to finish the load handling of the cargo. Reason for that can be, for example, that the container is mechanically damaged.

Our target was also to find methods to improve the situational awareness of the driver inside the cabin. Solutions which were developed for snow groomers and excavators can be utilized also in reach stacker applications when the driver is sitting inside the cabin. For example, we tested led-bars indicating presence of the obstacles near the machine in reach stacker's cabin. We also checked feasibility of the thermal camera for manual operation to detect humans near the machine in poor visibility conditions. From both cases we got valuable insights into productization work. The terminals where our reach stackers are working are often really congested and there is no extra space in layouts.

Kalmar participated in the human-centred design method workshops through iterative prototyping sessions organized by VTT. Our protoshop workers and engineers participated to those sessions and gave feedback for VTT developers to improve the UX features for next version. Kalmar also participated to interviews where research scientists from TUD collected feedback from reach stacker operators in seaports. User testing and interviews provides a structured approach to design XR interfaces that are intuitive, safe, and at same time effective. We try to utilize these methods in future development of our user interfaces. We will also continue collaboration with research scientists in upcoming EU-funded research projects where XR systems are in a central theme.

Kalmar is utilizing VTT's simulation solution in research projects and as a demonstrator in collaborative initiatives, helping partners and customer representatives to explore the potential of XR for remote operation, safety enhancements, and operator training. Kalmar developed also own version of the simulator where we utilized real SW and HW components of the control system. It can be utilized for remote controlled reach stackers, but also for versions where driver is controlling the machine inside the cabin. So, we could test XR solution for both versions.

The VTT's solution together with our solution enabled seamless transition between real-world and virtual environments, enhancing situational awareness, safety and operational efficiency. These capabilities are particularly relevant for training, planning, and real-time decision-making in complex environments like busy seaports and industrial sites. Kalmar will continue developing these concepts in collaboration with technology providers and our customers, aiming to integrate concepts into our control system products and for all our cargo handling machine models.

Kalmar's target is to commercialise these results developed in the THEIA^{XR} project in next generation control systems for different machine models. Remote control is needed always when we have increased automation level of the machine so much that one remote operator can operate several machines efficiently. Remote control is needed in fully automated or autonomous machines. In those cases, operator can assist the machine when it is not capable to execute the given task, for example when container is damaged. The results

will be used also when we are developing the cabins of our machines to be more user friendly, safer and productive. Kalmar will work closely with research partners to apply and adapt new XR methods and tools to our future challenges. These collaborations will help Kalmar to keep technology forerunner position in tough global competition.

Kalmar will also use the project outcomes in future development of our remote-controlled systems. We are putting more intelligence onboard the machine and with that it is possible to avoid operators causing collisions and accidents. With AR/VR technologies it is possible to show the user what machine has detected and what it is going to do next.

Furthermore, the results will be shared to all Kalmar divisions through workshops, demonstrations, and co-design sessions. These engagements will help raise awareness of the potentials of XR technologies and foster a culture of innovation and experimentation in different divisions. By embedding the results into our ongoing development and innovation activities, Kalmar ensures that the impact of THEIA^{XR} extends well beyond the project's duration to normal R&D work, supporting long-term advancements in safety, efficiency, and user experience in complex industrial and terminal environments.

5.2 Knowledge Enhancement & Community Outreach

Partner TUD:

TUD's exploitation plan builds upon its role as a leading research organisation. Accordingly, the results of the project are integrated into lectures and educational programmes at the university, ensuring that new knowledge is transferred directly to students and young researchers. Furthermore, the outcomes are disseminated as reference materials and case studies to support future research initiatives and to promote continued innovation in the field.

TUD's main contributions within the project include:

- a) the development of a multi-modal cabin mock-up for rapid and early HMI/XR design prototyping,
- b) the implementation of an LED-matrix display as an exterior HMI component for excavators,
- c) the creation of an LED-based collision warning indicator, and
- d) the integration of a LIDAR-based mapping functionality for 3D machine control systems.

These results have been actively communicated to both academic and industrial stakeholders and will serve as a foundation for future research collaborations with partners from the construction and related sectors, particularly in the field of XR technologies. The multi-modal cabin mock-up, in particular, offers significant potential for transfer to other domains such as forestry, logistics, and agriculture, where similar HMI and XR applications can be developed and evaluated.

Simulation-based and human-centred design methodologies have been further embedded in TUD's ongoing research and teaching activities. This approach has already been successfully implemented in several educational formats and research projects and will continue to be expanded in the future. The demonstration of advanced visualisation technologies as both external and cabin-integrated HMI components is expected to generate additional benefits across multiple domains.

Furthermore, the results are utilized as an important reference for forthcoming national and European research and innovation initiatives.

Overall, the project's outcomes have enhanced TUD's research capacities, strengthened the link between academia and industry, and contributed to the advancement of the European science and technology community.

Partner TUG:

TUG's exploitation plan for the THEIA^{XR} project is consistent with the intents and strategic goals of the European funding programs.

TUG's contributions to the THEIA^{XR} project include, amongst many minor developments, certain key results pending future exploitation, such as follows:

1. A combined laser and DLP system including a camera for outdoor projective Augmented Reality, enabling the visualization of information and instructions by way of AR in environments where head-worn glasses are prohibitive and handheld devices are inappropriate.
2. a panoramic thermal camera including two fisheye cameras for 360° panoramic RGB imaging, for safety applications and 3D reconstruction of outdoor environments, facilitating person detection and the investigation of certain environmental properties, such as surface temperature and condition.
3. a fully integrated VR experience for remote toy car driving, including steering wheel and pedal control, distance sensing and odometry, to study and investigate several research questions, such as depth perception and communication latency, for future use in environments with no physical access (e.g. disaster scenarios); and
4. methods and algorithms for infrastructure visualization by way of handheld AR devices, to prevent utility strikes in construction and to improve the understanding of situated utility locations, as well as approaches to digitally annotate and verify excavated utilities for further digitalization of infrastructure data.

All those results will be exploited through direct research collaboration with industry, integration into future research proposals, and as foundational assets for advancing XR technologies in operational and training contexts.

The laser and DLP projection system is currently undergoing further upgrades in terms of the used computational platform, and will likely be further investigated as an option to guide operators in scenarios like snow grooming, requiring further research concerning the size factor and the feasibility to automatically display certain available information from the outside. Another interesting aspect in terms of future research concerns the option to control the visualization in a static setup using knowledge about the viewer/operator viewing direction, which raises more interesting questions for view-dependent visualization and rendering. The developed system is therefore interesting for several practical areas, such as industries, but also in the context of entertainment or art (i.e. museum exhibitions).

The latest iteration of the omnidirectional panoramic thermal camera is fully rugged and has been shown to be useful in certain scenarios, being able to sense information around a machine or operator beyond the visible spectrum. Further research concerns the fusion and registration of the sensed data across modalities, such that a 3-dimensional model of the environment is built. This includes the integration of a LIDAR sensor to infer distances and to build a real 3D reconstruction. The combination of all those technologies enables a multimodal experience for a viewer for further investigation, which is of particular interest to several industries, including automotive, machine inspection, or maintenance.

While building a VR experience for a remote toy car including sensors and cameras does not immediately appear as a serious research task, several questions have been raised throughout the development. A preliminary use study has shown that typical monocular camera systems, despite potentially offering a full 360° field of view, still suffer from severe deficiencies, such as still being monocular. First attempts to reconstruct depth perception for an operator has shown to be very promising, and additional work is currently undertaken to reduce communication latency and to improve interaction agility. Several scenarios for further exploitation exist, involving even defensive military and civil protection in disaster scenarios.

Developing algorithms and systems for infrastructure visualization has been a traditional field for research at TUG for years. The latest iterations of our developments include a set of algorithms and methods for accurate outdoor localization, data management, and visualization. Those developments strengthen the role of TUG as a provider of key technology in accessible methods for infrastructure visualization and data handling by way of XR technology. Plans foresee academic-industrial cooperation with infrastructure providers to bring

this technology into practice. Dedicated publicly co-funded projects in infrastructure maintenance are currently of particular interest.

TUG as an academic institution does not actively and commercially exploit results developed in the THEIA^{XR} project. Instead, the focus is on leveraging these outcomes to strengthen TUG's research capabilities, deepen collaboration with Austrian and European industry, and contribute to the broader scientific and technological ecosystem. Therefore, the results will be used in several research projects, in which TUG works with industrial partners on several problems with the goal of introducing the developed XR methods and tools to real-world challenges. All those activities and collaborations will help in validating the solutions in operational environments and generate new insights for further research.

Simultaneously, the findings will act as a foundation for crafting new research proposals under Horizon Europe and various national funding initiatives. They establish a robust starting point for tackling upcoming calls related to human-machine interaction, immersive technologies, and digital transformation within industrial environments. TUG will also leverage these results to shape the trajectory of future research by engaging in expert panels, participating in standardization activities, and disseminating findings through scientific publications and conferences. This approach ensures that the knowledge generated in THEIA^{XR} continues to progress and guides the creation of next-generation XR systems.

Additionally, the findings will be disseminated via workshops, demonstrations, and co-design sessions with stakeholders from various sectors including logistics, construction, space, and manufacturing. These activities will enhance awareness of the potential of XR technologies and promote a culture of innovation and experimentation. By integrating the findings into its ongoing research and innovation initiatives, TUG ensures that the influence of THEIA^{XR} continues far beyond the project's timeframe, aiding in long-term improvements in safety, efficiency, and user experience in complex operational settings.

Partner UL:

UL exploitation plan for the THEIA^{XR} project taking into account the University of Luxembourg role in the project as research organisation, therefore the results are planned to be used in the purposes for fostering future education programs of University of Luxembourg and make a path for future European Collaboration on the guiding principles of XR technologies development for the industry.

UL contributions to the THEIA^{XR} project include the following results: a) an application and reporting theory-driven methods for analysis of aspects of usable security and privacy b) development and dissemination of "Privacy and Ethics Guidelines for Extended Reality Implementations in the Off-Highway Machinery Domain". The results will be exploited through active collaboration with different kinds of academic and non-academic stakeholders (e.g. non-commercial initiatives as XRSI) for incorporating our findings in educational programs in responsible XR development, Digital Ethics and User-Centred Security Design.

The methodological contribution exploitation

During the project we developed and adapted a battery of methods from Privacy Engineering (e.g. LinDDun Go, Z-inspection) and value-sensitive design (development of the workshop for core values, integrating the sentence completion method and questionnaires about core values into the assessment of the results etc.). This work can be used for educating the different academic and industrial actors how to apply human-centered design principles to the task of creating and evaluating the design processes from the point of preserving privacy and ethics of work in the context of industrial machinery. We already incorporated the demonstration of our methods to the course in **Master of Cybersecurity and Cyberdefence in the University of Luxembourg (Human-Centered Security Design)** and designing the **battery of methodological workshops, oriented toward broader industry** for the full-cycle support of ethical industrial XR designing initiative.

The Privacy and Ethics Guidelines for Extended Reality Implementations in the Off-Highway Machinery Domain exploitation

We are planning the following ways to exploit the developed Privacy and Ethics Guidelines for Extended Reality Implementations in the Off-Highway Machinery Domain exploitation (hereafter referred to as the Guidelines). The first way is raising awareness of the current state of development of XR technologies from the Ethical point of view. For that we planning to present our Guidelines for multiple EU events, which brings together different stakeholders on EU level (developers, legislators, industrial use-case holders). The aim will be to join the current standardisation and legislation initiatives in further iterations of European Code of Conduct for XR ethics (focusing on industrial applications). We already use our Guidelines to leverage discussion with EU commissioners and sister EU projects, which developing XR initiatives in industrial domain. We plan to continue this work by co-organising open sessions for our Guidelines and participating in working groups in XR ethics.

Both results (methodology for human-centered analysis of privacy and ethics in industrial XR and the Guidelines) will also be used for contributing to the development of the next EU and national level proposals related to industrial XR development

Partner HdM:

HdM is active in education, research, knowledge transfer projects and industrial projects all around the subjects of usability and user experience research and design, human-centric design and positive psychology. Methods explored and results of the project will directly feed into teaching and knowledge transfer activities, e.g., in the currently running co-design lecture (started in October 2024) or in the project Mittelstand Digital-Zentrum Fokus Mensch (started in 2023), which is aimed at German small and medium-sized enterprises and where the HdM is in a lead role. Especially the progress in exploring and validating the transdisciplinary co-design approach employed in THEIA^{XR} in a technical R&I context may affect the direction of research and teaching in the respective HdM work group and beyond. Contacts made with companies, institutions and partner projects may extend the reach and thematic work of the work group. A master thesis related to the project has been completed and two doctoral theses leaning closely on the THEIA^{XR} co-design procedure are currently being worked on.

The HdM has developed and conducted a novel transdisciplinary co-design approach in the project, which has resulted in a set of function, information and interaction concepts for the off-highway vehicle use cases targeted in the project. Thus, there are two key exploitable results from HdM:

- The newly developed and tested transdisciplinary co-design approach itself
- The validated, end-user-approved concepts resulting from this approach

The HdM, being a university of applied sciences, will exploit these results in four ways:

- In teaching, integrating the results in existing and new lectures within the B.A. information design course at the faculty of information and communication. One lecture on the application of co-design has been running for two semesters already and is being continued currently.
- In consulting and training services for enterprises and startups in contract-based industry projects.
- In training and support for small and medium-sized enterprises in digital transformation offered as part of the nationwide project “Mittelstand-Digital Innovation Hub Focus Human” (Mittelstand-Digital Zentrum Fokus Mensch). This is funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy. Services such as public events, workshops, projects, demonstrations, etc. are free of charge for small and medium-sized enterprises and serve to raise awareness and provide training in the areas of human-centered innovation and design.
- In future externally funded research and innovation projects, both national and international (Horizon Europe)

Partner VTT:

VTT's exploitation plan for the THEIA^{XR} project is consistent with its non-profit research role and strategic goals in European and Finnish industrial collaboration.

VTT's contributions to the THEIA^{XR} project include three key results: (1) a human-centred design method leveraging early-stage XR prototypes, (2) a design simulation solution for remote operations concept design, and (3) seamless transition methods along the VR/AR continuum. These results will be exploited through direct research collaboration with industry, integration into future research proposals, and as foundational assets for advancing XR technologies in operational and training contexts.

The human-centred design method developed through iterative prototyping and user testing provides a structured approach for designing XR interfaces that are intuitive, safe, and effective. This method will be applied in future co-design activities with industrial partners, particularly in logistics and heavy machinery sectors, to support the development of user-centric XR systems. It also serves as a methodological asset in upcoming EU-funded projects where human-machine interaction is a central theme.

The design simulation solution for remote operations offers a validated framework for developing XR-based control systems for off-highway machinery. It includes interaction concepts, visual guidance systems, and evaluation protocols that can be adapted to various industrial domains. VTT will use this solution in bilateral research projects and as a demonstrator in collaborative initiatives, helping partners explore the potential of XR for remote operation, safety enhancement, and operator training.

The seamless transition methods along the VR/AR continuum enable fluid movement between real-world and virtual environments, enhancing situational awareness and operational efficiency. This capability is particularly relevant for training, planning, and real-time decision-making in complex environments. VTT will continue developing this concept in collaboration with technology providers and industrial users, aiming to integrate it into broader XR ecosystems and future research on collaborative and multi-user XR environments.

As a non-profit research organization, VTT does not pursue direct commercialization of the results developed in the THEIA^{XR} project. Instead, the focus is on leveraging these outcomes to strengthen VTT's research capabilities, deepen collaboration with Finnish and European industry, and contribute to the broader scientific and technological ecosystem. The results will be actively used in bilateral research projects, where VTT works closely with industrial partners to apply and adapt the developed XR methods and tools to real-world challenges. These collaborations will help validate the solutions in operational environments and generate new insights for further refinement.

In parallel, the results will serve as a foundation for new research proposals under Horizon Europe and national funding programs. They provide a strong baseline for addressing future calls related to human-machine interaction, immersive technologies, and digital transformation in industrial settings. VTT will also use the outcomes to influence the direction of future research by participating in expert groups, contributing to standardization efforts, and publishing findings in scientific journals and conferences. This ensures that the knowledge generated in THEIA^{XR} continues to evolve and inform the development of next-generation XR systems.

Furthermore, the results will be shared through workshops, demonstrations, and co-design sessions with stakeholders across sectors such as logistics, construction, space and manufacturing. These engagements will help raise awareness of the potential of XR technologies and foster a culture of innovation and experimentation. By embedding the results into its ongoing research and innovation activities, VTT ensures that the impact of THEIA^{XR} extends well beyond the project's duration, supporting long-term advancements in safety, efficiency, and user experience in complex operational environments.

6 Business Model Considerations

6.1 Summary and Major Findings

Given the technical achievements and the definition of the exploitable results, activities in T7.2 clustered the findings of the result owners in separate versions of the canvas. These are provided in the following sub-sections and provide a consolidated view of the use-case participants on their application domain. Individual domain specific aspects are described and listed below.

6.2 Business Model Canvas – UC Snow Grooming

Figure 29 summarizes the analysis of the dedicated business model targeting the project UC on snow grooming utilizing the canvas methodology.

Figure 29: Summarized Analysis of the Business Model concerning UC Snow Grooming

6.2.1 Specific Circumstances in the Use Case Domain

The European market for XR technologies in the snow groomer business domain has been developing from futuristic concepts to operational demonstrators recently. Such concept installations have been presented on dedicated trade shows as mentioned in Section 2 of this report. The consortium has identified that **the current state is early stage but rapidly advancing**, with key players like Prinoth, Creanex, and TDA deploying initial systems and showcasing clear benefits in training effectiveness and safety. **The future outlook is that XR simulators will become an integral part of operator training** among forward-looking ski operations in Europe and abroad. The major specifics in this business area related to the exploitable results are:

- **Year-Round and On-Demand Training:** Snow groomer operation is seasonal – real machines typically run only in winter months, leaving a narrow window to train newbies on the job. XR simulators remove this limitation. A resort can train staff *pre-season* (e.g. in autumn) using XR/VR so they hit the ground running when snow falls. This flexibility leverages the efficiency when slopes open, since the operators already have hours of practice. Moreover, if an operator needs remedial training or if a new feature (say, a new grooming implement) is introduced, a simulator session can be setup and scheduled immediately. The burthen of delays caused by appropriate weather conditions or spare machine availability can be lifted. **The result is a more skilled workforce ready when needed**, which ultimately contributes to better-maintained ski slopes.
- **Complexity of Modern Machines:** Snow groomers are high-tech vehicles now, often equipped with electronic controls, telematics (e.g. snow depth sensors), and assistance systems. XR is an ideal way

to familiarize operators with these systems. For example, Prinoth’s latest models have features like on-board slope geometry maps, or even prototype **“Smart Snow” functions (object detection, auto speed limiting in sensitive areas)**. A simulator can teach drivers to use these advanced tools in a hands-on way. As machinery becomes more sophisticated, experiential learning via simulation shortens the technology adoption curve. This is similar to aviation where simulators help pilots manage complex avionics before they ever fly.

- **Shared Training Centers (OpEx model):** Given not every ski area can afford or justify a full simulator, we may see **regional training centers or academies** equipped with simulators that offer training as a service. For instance, an Alpine country could have a central snow grooming training facility where multiple resort companies send their drivers for certification courses that include simulator sessions. These centers could be run by industry associations, equipment manufacturers (e.g. Prinoth Academy might establish such a simulator hub), or private training companies. The business model here is **tuition/fees per trainee**. This lowers the barrier for resorts – instead of buying, they pay per use. It also keeps the simulator highly utilized with a steady stream of trainees from different clients.

6.3 Business Model Canvas – UC Logistics

Figure 30 depicts the analysis of the dedicated business model targeting the project UC on logistics utilizing the canvas methodology.

Figure 30: Summarized Analysis of the Business Model concerning UC Logistics.

6.3.1 Specific Circumstances in the Use Case Domain

In seaport logistics, **extended reality** – encompassing virtual and augmented reality – is emerging as an enabling technology for improving the reach stacker operations. Reach stackers (e.g. those by KAL) are heavy vehicles for moving shipping containers, and XR technologies can be integrated like demonstrated in the project to **improve training, safety, and efficiency**. For example, leading firms like Kalmar have deployed VR simulators that let operators practice container handling in a realistic virtual port, reducing the need for costly on-site training and minimizing wear on actual equipment. Simultaneously, **augmented reality** solutions have been successfully demonstrated in the project’s use-case to assist reach stacker drivers during operations – overlaying digital cues (like alignment guides and hazard alerts) on live camera feeds or displays. These cues help operators position containers more precisely and detect hidden obstacles or people in the yard, thereby **boosting situational awareness and preventing accidents**.

The major benefits can be listed as follows:

- **Operational Efficiency:** XR technologies yield clear efficiency gains in reach stacker operations. Better-trained drivers mean smoother; faster container moves and less damage.

- **Workforce Training & Skill Development:** XR is revolutionizing training for port equipment operators. Traditional training on real machines is time-consuming, costly, and potentially risky, with VR simulation.
- **Safety Improvements:** Safety is a paramount concern in ports, and XR offers **substantial safety benefits** for reach stacker operations.

Overall, by blending virtual and real-world information, XR adoption in port logistics promises safer, more efficient container handling and gives early adopters a competitive edge in throughput and workforce development. Utilizing the technologies showcased in this use-case and given the analysis of the stakeholders in Fig XX the opportunity of generating a viable business is promising and will foster the innovation cycles for this particular industry.

6.4 Business Model Canvas – UC Construction

Figure 31 provides the analysis of the dedicated business model targeting the construction domain utilizing the canvas methodology.

Figure 31: Summarized Analysis of the Business Model concerning UC Construction.

6.4.1 Specific Circumstances in the Use Case Domain

The adoption of extended reality and virtual reality in the construction machinery sector is accelerating. Both academic pilots and commercial deployments demonstrate how XR/VR can enhance operator safety, efficiency, and training. The project use-case on construction uses augmented displays to make hidden hazards and grade information visible in real time. These AR enhancements let operators catch grade deviations, potential collisions, or model errors at a glance, without diverting their eyes to secondary monitors. The most important benefits using the technologies in this domain are:

- **Enhanced Operator Awareness and Safety:** A central trend is using augmented reality to present critical information directly in the operator’s field of view, thereby improving situational awareness.
- **Virtual reality simulators for excavators** and other machinery create an immersive, 3D environment where trainees can practice operating controls, digging trenches, and reacting to scenarios without risking actual equipment or injuries.
- **Safety and Effectiveness:** VR training allows novice operators to learn from mistakes with zero risk – e.g. a new operator can experience a machinery fault or a near-miss with a virtual pedestrian in the simulator and learn proper responses, all in a controlled setting.

In industry, companies like Trimble and Bobcat are integrating XR. The solution by Trimble’s Earthworks system overlays 3D designs onto the real worksite through the excavator’s display, and Bobcat (with LG) has

prototyped a transparent AR windshield showing underground utilities and camera views in the operator's line of sight. Key use-cases range from VR simulators for operator training (providing risk-free, immersive practice) to augmented reality heads-up displays (HUDs) for on-site guidance and remote operation of machinery.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the final status of the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities that were planned at the beginning of the THEIA^{XR} project and those that have been carried out across the tasks T7.1 and T7.2 within the Work Package 7. Although there are task leads for the tasks T7.1 and T7.2, it didn't mean that these partners were in charge of carrying out the activity by their own. All partners involved in the THEIA^{XR} were actively contributing to the success of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the project results.

The deliverable presented an overview of various dissemination activities at public, scientific, and industrial level, along with the final results from these activities. It also showcases a selection of communication materials developed within the project, such as the project website, social media channels and various flyers. During Task 7.1, in the second phase, the consortium continued with "community outreach and result dissemination" and followed up with phase three "global outreach and sustainable impact" until the end of the project. Throughout the second phase of THEIA^{XR}, additional materials have been made available for project partners to use for informing different audiences (general, industrial, and scientific) about the project and its final technical outcomes. The co-design methodology has continued to engage with end-users of the technologies developed in the project to foster the potential impact of the solutions and concepts provided.

As mentioned in introduction the goal of the THEIA^{XR}'s exploitation activities in Task 7.2 is to ensure that the maximum value is created by the results generated, considering the different options of exploitation as defined in the project's exploitation strategy, defining specific paths to bring the results to their academic, industrial, and commercial uptake.

The final report on impact analysis, as presented herein, summarizes the activities performed in the reporting period M18-M36. According to the exploitation framework established in the project these activities have focused on the business models, exploitation strategies of project partners considering the achieved project results and further analysis of the characteristics of individual innovation items. Additionally, use-case specific business model canvas have been presented and the main considerations specific for the application domain have been summarized.

This was then the last step after an incremental process, to define at the best of the consortium knowledge the most suitable implementation roadmap for THEIA^{XR} results addressing the project results continuation and implementation roadmaps also at "company" level, thus more tangibly linking the results achieved and demonstrated by project activities to the development strategies and roadmaps of its partners.